

PROBONO

D1.4 GBN Strategic Vision and KPI Formalisation (FINAL)

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DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life². Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal³, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)⁴ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁵ and Renewable Energy Communities⁶ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensures just transition that maximise the economic and social co-benefits considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a standardised framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

¹ Please refer to the last submitted reports for the latest status of the definitions

² <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>

³ European_Green_Deal_EN_200710_fin

⁴ SET-Plan Action 3.2: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan.pdf

⁵ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 5 Renewable Energy Directive (EU)

⁶ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001/2018/2001

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁷ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁸ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁹ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
3PL	Third-party logistics
BIM	Building Information Modelling
COP	Conference of Parties
CSR	Corporate social responsibility
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Environmental Agency
EEEF	European Energy Efficiency Fund
EGR	Extensive Green Roof
EIB	European Investment Bank
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
ETF	Exchange-traded fund
GBF	Bioclimatic (Green) Building Funds
GBN	Green Building Neighbourhood s
GET	Green Economy Transition
HEGR	Highly Evaporative Green Roof
IBPC	International Biodiversity & Real Estate Council
IFC	Industry foundation classes
IGR	Intensiv Green Roof
kg/year	Kilogram per year
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
kWh/m ² /year	Kilowatt per square metre per year
LL	Living Lab
MFF	Multiannual Financial Framework
MMSSC	Maturity Model for Smart Sustainable Communities

Acronym	Description
MNN	Madrid Nuevo Norte
NGEU	NextGenerationEU
PA	Paris Agreement
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
RRP	Recovery and Resilience Plan
SCF	Supply chain finance
SEEDS	Sustainable Environment and Ecological Development Society
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SRI	Socially responsible investment
SSCF	Sustainable supply chain finance
tCO2-eq	Tonne of carbon dioxide equivalent
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WSIP	Walmart Sustainability Index Program

Executive summary

Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBN) is a comprehensive concept for sustainable neighbourhoods that takes into account technical, economic and social aspects, considering the entire life cycle from planning, construction and operation to demolition. The development of GBNs is highly complex, which is why it is important that all stakeholders involved have a common vision for the GBN and a strategy for its implementation, as well as a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) to characterize the GBNs accordingly.

In this document, some relevant aspects of GBNs are explained in detail to show their influence on GBN development. In chapter 3.1, it is shown why a human-centered simulation of technical systems should be carried out in the GBN and which aspects of social sustainability should be considered for this.

The maturity of GBNs must be measurable and should harmonize with international standards if possible. Therefore, the ISO 37100 series is used in PROBONO as the basis for describing and quantifying criteria (see chapter 3.2). The ISO 37107 Maturity Model for Smart Sustainable Communities provides a top-level maturity model for smart sustainable communities and can be used by project developers for self-assessment.

Measures to adapt to climate change and increase resilience are an important aspect of GBNs. Furthermore, an increasing number of hot days and an increasing demand for cooling can be expected, which is why measures to improve the microclimate should be implemented, e.g. greening facades or roofs. Measures to increase resilience to natural hazards are also important and are described in chapter 3.3.

By implementing green roofs and green facades, GBNs can also contribute to maintaining and increasing biodiversity. The importance of biodiversity and the possibilities for promoting it in GBNs are therefore discussed in chapter 3.4. This chapter explains in detail what is necessary in practice to actually successfully enhance biodiversity. For example, it is necessary to understand the ecosystem and the specific surroundings of the local GBN site.

Further technical aspects such as the use of renewable energies and the increase of energy efficiency, resource-efficient construction and intelligent planning and operation using digital twins are not specifically addressed in this document, but are being worked on in other WPs of PROBONO and are equally imperative to achieve the GBN objectives.

Successful implementation of GBNs is only possible if attractive financing options are available. To this end, financing instruments must adequately take into account the advantages of GBNs. ESG reporting (Environment, Social, Governance) is an important concept for demonstrating the advantages of GBNs. Chapter 4.1 describes how the ESG perspective can be used to develop GBNs and improve financing conditions. Furthermore, the availability of financing instruments and funding is crucial for the successful implementation of GBNs. Therefore, in chapter 4.2, the investment conditions of GBNs and the financing instruments provided by the European Union and other European institutions were examined and presented in detail.

The framework conditions for the practical development of GBNs are constantly changing. In chapter 4.3, the changes that have occurred in the PROBONO Living Labs in the first 36 months of the project are presented. These examples help to understand how the implementation strategy and the KPIs can be repeatedly adapted to real-world conditions. However, the overarching goals, such as climate neutrality or a high quality of stay for users, should not be called into question.

An important result of the work mentioned is the development of a GBN Target Model that helps project developers to successfully integrate the GBN aspects into their own projects. The integrated GBN Target Model describes the vision for a specific GBN and the associated implementation strategy. How the model can be developed from the various components is described in chapter 2.

1 Introduction

To limit climate change and achieve the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and the EU's Green Deal targets, our buildings and cities must become sustainable and climate-neutral. Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBN) describe a concept for sustainable buildings that also benefit from shared utility structures in neighbourhoods.

The strategic vision of GBNs is to strengthen the construction and renovation of sustainable buildings and associated infrastructure, in particular energy supply and mobility, by incorporating neighbouring buildings and implementing cooperative solutions such as shared energy use. To this end, an integrated approach is pursued in which all important aspects such as energy, mobility, digitization and social issues such as comfort, quality of life and affordability of housing are taken into account in the planning. Sustainability aspects should also be taken into account in all phases of the neighbourhood's life, from planning and construction to operation and demolition, for example by making greater use of digital tools. In addition, efforts are being made to specifically consider the relevant economic evaluation criteria when designing GBNs in order to facilitate their financing.

To implement this vision and achieve a holistic approach, it is necessary to consider various aspects and dimensions of the neighbourhood and its development and to evaluate GBNs using key performance indicators (KPIs). In PROBONO, a set of KPIs was developed in WP 6 to characterize GBNs and to verify whether specific neighbourhood projects meet GBN objectives (Antolin and et al. 2022a, 2022b). This document explains various important aspects of the development of GBNs in detail and describes the strategic vision derived from them. Which KPIs are considered and monitored in the evaluation of the Living Labs (LL) in PROBONO is not the subject of this document, but is described in (Antolin and et al. 2024).

1.1 Mapping PROBONO Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map PROBONO's GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
T1.2 GBN Vision and KPI Formalisation [M3-M32]	ST1.2.1 GBN Vision specification tools. Integrate an ESG perspective used by investors in capital markets to understand corporate behaviour regarding ESG and use it as one of the key metrics determining corporate future financial performance (return and risk). This is underpinned by the ESG framework, which will be built on a sector, asset and territory basis leveraging existing Moata ESG tools that link the benefits of 'smart technology' solutions, based on the premise that investments in technology must stem from clear benefits to citizen initiatives.	Section 2	Sustainability framework and tools (SEEDS, ProBIM, Fresk) and the ISO 37100 standards, and the 37107 MMSSC (maturity model for smart sustainable communities) for strategic DSS. Analysis of biodiversity and climate adaptation resilience measures (sections 2.3 and 2.4)
T1.2 GBN Vision and KPI Formalisation [M3-M32]	ST1.2.2 Investment Analysis. Identify the context of specific financing options available to investors and developers of sustainable developments specially to understand the relation between the more traditional financing available, such as through either equity or through debt issuance (bonds) relative to the main drivers for incorporating ESG for investors, being financial performance and regulation. This will include analysis of the recently published set of EU disclosures that funds must adhere to if they want to be marketed in the EU and that non ESG equity or bonds will therefore carry an issuance premium as they won't be able to be added to certain funds.	Section 3.1 to 3.3	Financing options for GBNs, and sustainable supply chain finance, (SSCF) Section 3.2.
T1.2 GBN Vision and KPI Formalisation [M3-M32]	ST1.2.3 Living Lab Strategic Vision and KPI Formalisation. While the Strategic Vision and KPIs have preliminarily been set out, Living Lab needs may change. This work involves an update, capturing any changes at project start, to give accurate, timely and detailed ESG integration, financial planning and KPI's setting the baseline for evaluation in WP6. Subtask team.	Section 3.4	Strategic Vision and KPIs of the LLs in Section 3.4.
DELIVERABLE			
D1.4: GBN Strategic Vision and KPI Formalisation (FINAL) [32]: This report formulates the findings of T1.2, and explores step/s C) Investment opportunities identified. [C=M32] (PU)			

Table 1: Adherence to PROBONO's GA deliverables and tasks descriptions

1.2 Definition of strategic vision and KPI formalisation, purpose of the document

Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBN) is a very comprehensive concept for future-oriented and sustainable construction. The concept encompasses ecological, economic and social goals and attempts to achieve them through intelligent and resource-saving methods and technologies. In addition, the aim is to develop synergies through cooperation between buildings, for example in the form of energy communities.

In view of the large number of sub-aspects and the respective objectives, conflicting goals are unavoidable. Therefore, balanced solutions must be developed for GBNs that do justice to all sub-aspects to a sufficient extent and with the highest possible overall quality. In order to be able to carry out this process of deliberation and negotiation in a targeted manner, a common strategic vision for the GBN is needed, which the various actors can use as a guide. In addition, key indicators are needed that take into account the various sub-aspects according to their relevance.

This document presents some relevant aspects for the characterization of GBNs in detail, which were examined in PROBONO in tasks 1.1 and 1.2. Furthermore, it is shown how a strategic vision and the associated key indicators are developed from these and other aspects. The evaluation of the GBN demonstrators in PROBONO, on the other hand, is not the subject of this document.

1.3 Structure of the document and its relation with other WPS/Deliverable

This document describes the strategic vision developed in PROBONO for GBNs and the related KPIs that help to verify the achievement of the vision. It summarizes the work and results from the task “T1.2 Formalization of the GBN vision and performance metrics”. The basic technology-oriented requirements for GBNs were developed in Task “T1.1 GBN Analysis Tools and Decision Support System”.

In the framework of T1.1 and T1.2, a GBN Target Model was developed, which is presented in chapter 2. The model is introduced in chapter 2.1, practical implementation aspects are explained in chapter 2.2, the structure of a GBN is presented in chapter 2.3, the GBN integration and transition strategy is described in chapter 2.4 and as a summary a general GBN Target Model is provided in chapter 2.5.

In Chapter 3 “Technical-oriented decision support for GBN development”, basic aspects for the definition of GBNs are described, which are results of T1.1.

Chapter 3.1 explains how human-centered simulation can be used to increase the user-friendliness of GBN projects. The chapter summarizes the results of subtask "ST1.1.1 Simulation and Analysis".

Chapter 3.2 provides information on GBN maturity and summarizes the results of subtask "ST1.1.2 GBN Maturity Assessment".

Chapter 3.3 explains possible measures for climate change adaptation and for increasing the resilience of GBNs and is based on the work in "ST1.1.3 Climate adaptation and resilience tool".

The possibilities for increasing biodiversity are described in Chapter 3.4, which summarizes the findings from "ST1.1.4 Biodiversity option analysis".

In addition to the technical aspects of the development of GBNs described in chapter 3, chapter 4 describes additional metrics in the area of financing GBNs.

Chapter 4.1 highlights the integration of the ESG perspective (Environmental, Social, Governance) in the design of GBNs and summarizes the results of "ST1.2.1 GBN vision specification tools".

Chapter 4.2 describes the various financing mechanisms and options that can be used to implement GBNs and is based on the results of "ST1.2.2 Investment analysis".

The preliminary vision and associated KPIs developed in the PROBONO project planning had to be adapted based on the practical experience gained in the development of the demonstrators in the LLs. Therefore, chapter 4.3 describes the changes made to the strategic vision and KPIs in the LLs based on the work in "ST1.2.3 Living Lab Strategic Vision and KPI Formalisation".

Chapter 5 provides the conclusions of the document.

The work in WP 1 and especially in T1.1 and T1.2, which are presented in the overview in this document and on the basis of which the GBN target was developed, are relevant for all other WPs. However, this document is particularly closely linked to WP 6 "Monitoring and evaluation of the project's Living Labs", in which the KPIs are described and determined in detail, and to WP 7 "Living Labs GBN Implementation", in which the GBN concept is tested and demonstrated in practice.

A graphical overview of the assignment of chapters to individual subtasks is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Structure of D1.4 with assignment of chapters to individual subtasks

1.4 Contribution to creating GBN

The development of GBNs requires a shared vision of all stakeholders involved, which criteria the GBN should fulfill and a clear strategy for how the GBN should be designed and implemented. This includes the definition of KPIs, which can be used to check whether specific neighbourhood developments meet the requirements of GBNs.

In this context, the explanations in this document about the essential criteria of a GBN and the resulting vision and strategy make a decisive contribution to the successful implementation of GBNs. The illustration of the GBN Target Model and how it is developed, as described in Chapter 2, is particularly helpful in designing GBNs.

2 GBN Target Model

2.1 The GBN Target Model: What it is, why it's needed and how it works

PROBONO's GBN Target Model is a decision-making tool for local neighbourhood stakeholders at both policy and practitioner levels. It provides them with the required information they need

to implement sustainability activities at a neighbourhood level: to accelerate and complement sustainability outcomes and KPIs at wider district, city or even national levels. It is a sustainability integrator – an accelerator aligning local neighbourhood aims, objectives and outcomes to wider regional, national and even international imperatives.

At its core, PROBONO and its GBN Target Model aggregates and curates pre-existing sustainability strategies, initiatives and their KPI's, to deliver options, supporting measures and an evidence base to support additional neighbourhood initiatives. Addressing fresh local challenges and supporting the improvement of neighbourhood outcomes, through the express goal of delivering a business case. One that is aligned with and supportive of wider KPIs, whether at city, national or EU levels, yet orientated to local neighbourhood stakeholders and needs and the achievement of the sustainability outcomes they seek.

The GBN Target Model provides the essential guidelines, reference model and underlying structure by which local stakeholders can align their neighbourhood sustainability needs to wider KPIs and imperatives. Thus, de-risking their GBN business case through ensuring that their intended GBN concept and subsequent implementation of activities, complements and accelerates sustainability outcomes and stakeholder aims at levels outside of the immediate GBN.

The GBN Target Model amalgamates three pre-existing constructs - sustainable cities, resilient cities, and connected cities and brings them down to a neighbourhood level and more focussed and applicable to a GBN neighbourhood level. Of these, sustainable and resilient cities deliver a GBNs target goals while the latter, is a powerful catalyst at the local level to put these goals into practice. In addition, this local level connectivity embracing cities, local regions and municipalities as well as neighbourhoods, connects the GBN to higher level goals such as EU policy aims and KPIs along with wider international sustainability undertakings.

To fully begin to develop and implement a GBN Target Model, its concrete and abstract facets of the must be delineated. This is a way of effectively organising the information within the GBN Target Model so that it can be applied contextually by the different actors on the ground, whether policy or practitioner with their differing needs. This is done by breaking down and differentiating the Conceptual GBN, and the Practical GBN as discrete entities. The target model will outline these and work across them as a method for categorising all relevant parts and how scale up occurs.

2.1.1 The Conceptual GBN

A GBN – Green Building Neighbourhood, is a concept under development by the PROBONO H2020 project funded under the EU’s Horizon 2020 programme in support of the Green Deal. PROBONO’s early stage, conceptual description of a GBN states:

A GBN is an ecosystem of Natural, Physical, Technical and Social attributes, interacting within a wider System of Systems. A GBN aligns the human and natural world, reducing energy use through renewable, local sources and circular resources. A GBN aspires to a net positive impact on both humans and nature, operating in line with both the natural world and urban reality. It is an urban or rural ecosystem, which minimises human impact on the natural world, balancing both development and Quality of Life. A GBN is a people-centred social, urban and natural area, integrating natural and human infrastructures, through positive and sustainable collaboration.

At a conceptual level, all communities are nascent GBNs and this description provides a clear and aspirational narrative to support them mature. In practice, in real-world terms, how this aspiration translates and come together on the ground remains pivotal, particularly, its application, value and benefit to those seeking to make and mature the GBN journey for their neighbourhood (or community). To create a fully functioning GBN Target Model, therefore, there must be some common areas across which practical implementation can work.

So as to develop this sense of cohesion, the mapping to internationally agreed and recognised ISO standards is a crucial component of the target model across all levels, acting as a key coordination point for shared efforts between stakeholders which may otherwise struggle with translation of policy into practical actions (such as EU KPIs translated at a regional level). Furthermore, the implementation of this standardisation will free up actors at the various levels to take part in a more diverse and dynamic system of information interchange that acknowledges the plurality of the challenges facing the fields of sustainability and resilience, using connectivity across, within, and between localities, regional levels, and tiers of policy making and implementation. This will have the effect of scaling up the concept to a more holistic level that creates a diverse and flexible framework for individual LLs and municipalities via modelling the relationship between sustainability, resilience, and other metrics.

2.1.2 Establishment of a connection between sustainability and resilience

As part of its standardisation of EU goals and specific sub targets to meet within them at the local level, PROBONO delineates and explores the connection between sustainability and resilience within its GBN Target Model, thus accounting for real time change and factoring in

predicted outcomes of specific climate related metrics such as sea level rise of temperature increase into its operating structure.

PROBONO will recognise that resilient cities are often sustainable ones, due to their ability to withstand disasters. They are therefore less likely to need more resources in event of poor outcomes, leading to a smaller impact on local supply chains and official infrastructure. Nevertheless, it will also distinguish between the two descriptors, highlighting how sustainability does not always equal resilience, and vice versa. It will then identify, through ISO data as well as its other methods of lower level, local, and regional data where, if any, the connections between sustainability and resilience lie, and their relevance for policy implementation and decision making on the ground.

Through this, there is a significant advantage towards meeting KPIs by recognising that sustainability and resilience – as distinct metrics – often influence and interact with each other. PROBONO will investigate this aspect of meeting KPIs through modelling potential outcomes and matching these with initiatives and predictions for on the ground actors via techniques such as AI, ML and data aggregation. This will add an increased area of context to decision making as the core challenge at the local and regional level, facilitating it not just by providing access to more specific information through its use of KPIs and the specific ways of measuring them, but also through broadening the range, variety, and topics of usable and accessible data at the local level.

2.1.3 ISO Mapping as generation of common ground between actors

Despite the importance and validity of current EU KPIs within circular economies, sustainability, and the green deal per se, these guidelines and targets do not presently provide a detailed or granular enough framework for the actors on the ground to identify what would be the most efficient and powerful changes they could take. Therefore, the alignment to standards and particularly existing community/cities-related ISO standard is a core strategy of PROBONO towards mitigating the challenge of the lack of usable actionable data that is usable at the local urban level, including GBN.

Furthermore, the high level of risk vs reward often involved in making changes at the city or neighbourhood level, can sometimes disincentivise stakeholders from making efforts, despite the fact they may otherwise have both the desire and the infrastructure to do so. PROBONO will address this by translating and framing the main relevant KPIs (for example stemming from the ISO 37120 metrics) as a solution to this lack of specificity, operating in the form of an Integrator

for best practices, methods, tools and data, to help actors on the ground deal with the large amounts of information and the challenges that come from the complexity and connectivity within the reference frame of ISO37101 and ISO37104.

2.2 The Practical GBN

Having a conceptual framework and strategy for GBNs and importantly, for the PROBONO project, scaling up LLs into a GBN, is not enough. A practical reference model is required. A GBN, through its data, tools and techniques, is the translation of the Green Deal policies through practical innovations and activities, implemented at neighbourhood levels.

The Green Deal states “EU countries are committed to achieving climate neutrality by 2050, delivering on the commitments under the Paris Agreement. The European Green Deal is the EU’s strategy for reaching the 2050 goal. It supports the transformation of the EU into a fair and prosperous society with a modern and competitive economy” (European Commission 2024). Therefore, by necessity, a GBN must meet or at least work towards these targets to factor in social and political aspects of sustainability into its operating model.

Through identifying the range of activities under the Green Deal that can be translated to a neighbourhood level, benefitting local context and needs, a GBN in parallel creates an enabling bridge between building level renovations and city-wide plans, resulting in a GBN becoming a sustainability accelerator at neighbourhood-level and a crucial nexus of data exchange, supporting city-wide aims.

2.2.1 Synthesis of the final target model as a structure for evidence backed initiative dissemination

The need for a target model is evident to translate these green deal initiatives into practical action and thus, simplify the decision-making process for stakeholders. To do this, PROBONO has identified the gap between current data on sustainability initiatives in an area and the desired target model, called D, or delta.

For the initial and continuous development and improvement of the GBN target model, PROBONO facilitates a network of complementary data-based resources and measurements to de-risk and consolidate the development process. These include, but are not limited to, a range of data and tools such as those from Net Zero Cities, EU City Calculator and the EIB – European Investment Bank.

To put into action this tailored, data backed and local level support for decision makers, PROBONO uses a sequence of actions from KPI identification to policy implementation through its modelling, mapping, and decision-making tools. It will aggregate data from these metrics to compare, then contrast across levels of policy making to allow decision makers – policy or practitioner, to find the best methods for implementing the GBN Target Model.

The GBN Target Model exhibits a tiered structure, utilising bottom-up data generated from pre-existing, verified solutions to KPI based challenges. This will ensure the flow of data, solutions, and real time feedback both across and between stakeholders at the local and regional levels, as well as downwards from national and higher-level policy making tiers towards such stakeholders as local mayors, community leaders and urban planners and so on, better placed to implement neighbourhood solutions to meet the challenges they face.

2.2.2 Comparative analysis as a further validator

PROBONO transforms data to a highly usable form through comparative analysis highlighting how similar types of initiatives operate differently at different levels and both across and within levels.

This will create a further source of feedback and will increase the capacity for informed decision making by allowing local actors to identify which real life scenarios their own neighbourhoods are most similar. Subsequently mapping and modelling outcomes through PROBONO as a granular and differentiated decision making tool. In doing this, PROBONO will not just rely on categorising data but on working with it flexibly and dynamically to adapt to changing scenarios. This will enable the GBN perform as a dynamic system that adapts in response to initiatives outcomes, learned experience, and policy changes, giving it a powerful capacity to adapt to new circumstances and thus form stronger and more innovative relationships across levels, both locally and wider.

The data, tools, and techniques used to develop a GBN provide decision-makers, local actors, and stakeholders with the means and best practices to understand the range of available options for their neighbourhood. It also helps them plan, participate in, and measure initiatives aimed at achieving sustainability goals. These initiatives should align with the Green Deal and address multiple themes such as climate, environment, energy, transport, industry, agriculture, and sustainable finance.

In addition, GBN planning tools also help decision makers identify and facilitate the key supporting mechanisms that make a GBN possible: green finance, commissioning, procurement

and economic options and models for example. Also addressing how a GBN might be coordinated, managed and governed, through for example, the role of a GBN Integrator.

2.2.3 Aggregation of pre-existing initiatives through KPI based screening process

With the use of the ISO13100 framework as a basis to ensure standardisation and because it involves a comprehensive set of principles towards accelerating sustainability in cities and quality of life, integrating preservation and improving the environment, PROBONO aims to establish for GBNs a method for determining reliable and worthwhile initiatives at the neighbourhood level that align to key EU goals. This establishes the basic GBN Target Model methodology of integrating EU Goals with existing infrastructure to form the foundations of a GBN. PROBONO will then aggregate these goals within its structure and platform to make accessible for dissemination to relevant policy makers at a local level.

Case Study. PROBONO Madrid LL is an element of the Madrid Nuevo Norte (MNN) development, the most significant urban transformation project that Spain's capital city will undergo, and one of the most important in Europe. It is designed to improve citizens' life quality and create a more efficient, sustainable, and prosperous people-centred city, where public spaces, sustainable mobility, housing, offices, retail spaces, green areas, and public facilities are complementary. As a model that has included in some parts a citizen participative processes, it provides a reference for what a mature GBN Target Model might look like.

The Madrid GBN (PROBONO Ambition). The PROBONO LL in Madrid is a relatively small part of MNN, focussed on the Las Tablas district. It forms an integrated, integral part of the entire MNN development and wider sustainable ecosystem. It is showcasing a geothermal energy model, to become a Renewable energy Community as a basis for going beyond zero CO2 emissions. Establishing a positive energy balance through feasible technological and social solutions for both individual buildings set within broader green districts.

In this instance, specific data use including a deep literature review and desk analysis of both the MNN and wider Madrid's sustainability activities will establish a Green Deal initiative baseline. Followed by the application of both EU City Calc and ISO 37101 mapping (forming PROBONO's GBN maturity assessment tool) to assess both Las Tablas and MNNs activities against local/regional/national and international 2050 targets. In addition, Net Zero Cities initiatives aligning to the planning and development needs of a GBN will be considered as 5 of the 6 cities hosting a PROBONO LL (Aarhus, Brussels, Dublin, Madrid, and Porto) are Mission Cities of the EU-Mission "100 Climate-neutral and Smart Cities" (Net Zero Cities 2024). The Madrid LL will

form the basis for the GBN Target Model, to be further enhanced during the life of the project with additional aspects of the GBN, such as for finance, procurement, commissioning and the role of the GBN Integrator, through analysis and work with the Dublin LL.

PROBONO's GBN Target Model will, backed by data from the ISOs, use KPIs as a way of determining the relevance and suitability of initiative options, before sharing information that enables local neighbourhood policy makers to inform their business cases for onward implementation. This will ensure that initiatives have a prior history of success, via their ability to meet and align to specific KPIs. PROBONO will likewise be able to identify and highlight exactly which of these KPI initiatives to meet – and how – filling crucial gaps within decision making with validated, data backed information.

A PROBONO GBN will use data specifically from proven sources, coupled with on the ground research and specifically ISO 37120 (performance of city services and indicators of quality of life) as well as EU City Calc data and EIB Smart City data. It will also use the ISO 37123 indicators (city resilience to shocks and stresses) and 37122 (indicators for smart cities) as measurable outputs, whilst inputs will include smart initiatives (designed for connectivity), sustainability initiatives, and resilience initiatives. Likewise, it will gather metrics from the EEA (European Environmental Agency) to further create target outputs within a literature-scarce environment. Together, this is specifically designed to ensure that resultant GBN business cases are de-risked through their alignment to wider KPIs and needs.

2.2.4 Response to regional policy differences and solution comparison

As an aggregator, PROBONO will account for regional policy and legality differences by offering relevant data that is applicable to varying policy restrictions. This will happen through its use of real, on the ground, and previously tested initiatives that are data backed, thus showing quantitative results within a versatile range of landscapes of legality and policy.

Together, these provide a robust understanding for a GBN reference model – The GBN Target Model. This will be assessed against the PROBONO LLs (adapted to local context) and their Net Zero City initiatives, producing a gap analysis of maturity of each LL towards their GBN journey.

A GBN transition and integration strategy, contextualised to each neighbourhood LL is then produced. The proposed GBN Target Model gives a scalable, transferable benchmark and framework incorporating the political, economic, social, and environmental objectives desirable for a GBN. Furthermore, this will then support the design of a systematic and holistic

methodology for transitioning to sustainable and fair neighbourhoods. This can be seen in Figure 2 which shows the example for the Madrid LL GBN transition.

Figure 2: GBN transition and integration strategy

2.3 Structure to develop a GBN Target Model

Figure 3 sets out the structure and framework for the development of the GBN Target Model of a specific neighbourhood. It follows a logical and sequential format as being developed for the Madrid LL by PROBONO and then subsequently, further informed and updated from Dublin. It is intended as to act as a guide for decision-makers and can be contextualised and adapted dependent upon local circumstances and maturity of both the neighbourhood and the stakeholders within it.

Figure 3: Structure and framework for the development of a GBN target model

2.4 GBN Integration Models & Transition Strategies

This section outlines the strategic rationale for transitioning from LLs to GBNs within the PROBONO project. As well as providing an overview of the component parts of a LL to GBN Transition Strategy as will be documented in detail in D1.11c. This will provide the scope of a roadmap for this transition, supporting all project partners to understand their roles and contributions. It also addresses the challenges and opportunities associated with this transition, offering insights into best practices and strategic considerations.

2.4.1 Background Context

PROBONO aims to create sustainable urban environments by leveraging its LLs and showing their transition into GBNs. This transition is crucial for achieving long-term sustainability goals and enhancing the quality of life for all stakeholders. This section provides a strategic

framework, the basis of a roadmap for this transition, focusing on key components, stakeholder roles, and integration strategies.

PROBONO is a large-scale project involving numerous partners and addressing diverse needs. The initial assumptions made during the proposal stage often differ from the realities encountered on the ground. This discrepancy creates challenges in achieving a cohesive approach, as partners may struggle to understand how their roles contribute to the larger picture. Significant challenges within the project include the fact that it works across areas of diverse needs, as well as the challenges inherent in coordination of a project at such a large scale. The project addresses a wide range of needs, from technical and physical renovations to social aspects like behaviour change for better energy use. Likewise, ensuring effective coordination among various stakeholders is critical but challenging due to differing levels of understanding and engagement.

2.4.2 Strategic Rationale

This strategic rationale aims to enhance understanding and coordination among PROBONO partners, facilitating a smooth transition from LLs to GBNs.

To integrate the GBN target model, strategies will work across multiple levels in the same way that PROBONO has been developed as a connectivity strategy for finding standardization mechanisms and common ground between different stakeholders at policy and practice and local and wider levels.

These separate areas require their own unique methods of assessment in accordance with their individual needs and the variability within and across localities. However, they can largely be classified into the following areas, each with core developments for integration that become a part of the bedrock of the integration strategy.

2.5 A General GBN Target Model

To successfully integrate the GBN concept within any given Living Lab, there must first be the development of a General Target Model that can be adapted to individual localities. The basis for this will be outlined in chapter 3 and 4 of this document.

Since stakeholders in the LLs and elsewhere on the ground may lack specialist expertise in developing individual target models, the general model will classify information into core

categories that integrate the main challenges found within sustainability that a GBN - to meet its KPIs – should hope to address.

These categories can be summarized as follows, and exist within a wider matrix of strategies that must be implemented by a given locality to integrate any GBN, regardless of regional differences:

2.5.1 Assessment

The assessment stage of the target model governs the physical infrastructure and desired outcomes of the GBN. The assessment stage should cover the following processes:

- identification of core challenges within the target neighbourhood such as: sustainability, weather resilience, supply chain circularity, green energy and renewables, localized economies, social and community responsibility, infrastructure and facilities, nature protection and monitoring, and opportunities for science and innovation;
- analysis of the presence or absence of previously existing successful and unsuccessful strategies within sustainability and resilience;
- analysis of existing policy on implementation of new initiatives including potential areas of ease and challenge; and lastly, niches and opportunities for the implementation of new initiatives.

It is at this stage that more detailed and data driven assessments may take place such as energy auditing and stakeholder consultations and participatory design, given the need for the data derived from this in the latter stages of the target model development process. Metrics such as energy auditing are crucial for assessing and analysing existing niches, challenges, and opportunities as they give workable and concrete metrics by which stakeholders can collaborate.

2.5.2 Analysis

At the analysis level of creating the target model, relevant stakeholders should identify conflicts and solutions based off the previously examined factors within the assessment stage. These can and should include such elements as:

- clash between policy limitations and needs on the ground
- presence or absence of data on the efficacy of potential initiatives

- reasons for the success or lack thereof of past initiatives and prediction of how this could inform future decision making, and;
- identification of data and coordination gaps such as via a ‘stakeholder connections map’ to show the new opportunities and pre-existing collaborative relationships at both policy creation and community practice levels.

2.5.3 Integration

The integration stage of the GBN target model should identify pathways through which coordination of strategies can operate, whether these are networks within academia, policy and governance, community-based organisations, municipality and/or private sector and business organisations. It maps out and plans the target model for the GBN by sorting the information identified in the above stages and correlating it from PROBONO aggregator-based predictions and information share from strategic partners across the same and higher or lower levels of policy making.

2.5.4 Higher level policy development

These are all set out in detail in D1.11c and include:

- Integration with Existing Structures, including Policy Alignment;
- Phased Implementation: Monitoring and Evaluation;
- assessment and planning, including a baseline assessment and stakeholder connectivity;
- financing and auditing of pre-existing strategies for sustainability including green energy, nature-based solutions, recycled design materials, and local economies and food systems.
- Data connectivity and data-based solutions for improved sharing of crucial information across and between partners at varying levels of the covenant community structure.

The GBN Target Model will facilitate these goals by crossing the ‘data divide’ between generalised policies at the higher level and the need for usable KPIs at the lower levels of governance. It will bridge this by using data backed initiatives that are aggregated via PROBONO and can be mapped and modelled through AI and cross locality data sharing to predict how a given initiative may or may not affect an individual GBN.

Thus, this 'gap-focussed' method will ensure higher level policy can focus on a set of tangible and translatable goals that can operate efficiently at the levels of implementation – i.e. abstract systems that are also translatable into direct action. The target model can thus be formed loosely at the higher levels via the following steps and in tandem with the three core processes of assessment, analysis, and integration as outlined earlier in this section.

2.5.5 Human – Policy Interactions

Lastly, to effectively implement this policy or even translate it at the abstract stage into a GBN Target Model and by extension LL transition strategy, acknowledging the differentiated needs of stakeholders is a crucial component.

This can be done by the creation of stakeholder personas as outlined in GBN Prototypical Stakeholder Models (ST1.5.1) This is further broken down into the RACI Matrix: Defines roles, responsibilities, and accountabilities of GBN actors across the building lifecycle as well as Personas, which use real-life stakeholder experiences to support future implementations (Responsibility assignment matrix with role distinction Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed) (Wikipedia). The use of a RACI matrix and personas ensures that all stakeholders have a clear understanding of their roles and responsibilities, which is essential for effective coordination and implementation.

3 Basic decision support for GBN development

A variety of aspects need to be considered when developing GBNs. This chapter highlights and describes the aspects that were examined in more detail in PROBONO's Task 1.1. These include the human-oriented modelling approach for developing GBNs (chapter 3.1), the KPIs that can be used to measure the maturity of GBNs, in particular those described in the ISO 371 00 series (chapter 3.2), the measures for adaptation to climate change and for increasing resilience (chapter 3.3) and the measures for increasing biodiversity (chapter 3.4). Not shown, but just as important, for example, is a climate-neutral energy supply. The procedure for appropriate energy planning is explained in D4.1. Other aspects, such as resource-efficient construction or intelligent planning and operation with a digital twin, are also being worked on in PROBONO, but are not presented in detail here.

3.1 Human-centred simulation and analysis

Human-centric social values span and can be created at all levels of society. To further comprehend these concepts, they can be conceptualised as impacting three distinct but mutually dependent levels. These levels are: i) Global and governmental level, ii) City and neighbourhood level, and iii) Human-centred level, illustrated in Figure 4 ((Kamari et al. 2024) based on (Kristoffersen 2023)).

Figure 4: Illustration of the three levels of social values (Kamari et al. 2024)

The governmental and societal level focuses on values beyond being able to be addressed at a building and neighbourhood level or values that cannot directly be impacted by a building or at a neighbourhood level in a meaningful way. For example, these values, among others, include focuses on democracy and workers' rights (Kamari et al. 2024; Kristoffersen et al. 2024), as well as some of the broader concepts from the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals. Furthermore, the values related to the city and neighbourhood level are strongly focused on the interactions and actions that take place between buildings and neighbourhoods, such as crime rates, accessible infrastructure, and the formation of local communities (Kamari et al. 2024; Kristoffersen et al. 2024). On the other hand, as humans, on average, spend upward of 86.9% of their time indoors (Klepeis et al. 2001), focusing on social values on a human-centred scale in connection with the built environment can be seen as an impactful focus point, comparing the 7.6% time spent in outdoors and 5.5% time spent in a vehicle.

To ensure that a neighbourhood becomes a functioning GBN with thriving citizens that positively contribute to the neighbourhood, a large focus on the human-centred level of social values and

aspects is therefore of the utmost importance. The importance of satisfying the human-centred and more individually focused aspects is also in line with the depiction of Maslow's hierarchy of needs (Maslow 1943), where basic physiological and safety-oriented needs require to be fulfilled before the individual can participate in and pursue the fulfilment of higher-ranking needs (e.g. social needs). This further should be pursued when establishing a functioning GBN, as only humans who have fulfilled their basic human-centred wants and needs can participate and contribute towards the more complex social mechanisms that span the entire GBN.

In developing GBNs, it is, therefore, worth beginning with the values and aspects tied to the human-centred level, thereby focusing on the experience of the individual and social values related to the individual human's experience. This includes aspects and values such as comfort, health and wellbeing (Kamari et al. 2024; Kristoffersen et al. 2024). This scale of focus on socially oriented aspects is also echoed in prevailing building certification systems, such as BREEAM (BRE Global 2021), LEED (U.S. Green Building Council 2022), WELL (International WELL Building Institute 2020) and DGNB-DK (Green Building Council Denmark 2021). Although these building certification systems are commonly referred to as sustainability certification systems (Jensen and Birgisdottir 2018), their focus on the social aspect of sustainability is on selected social values instead of promoting the broader and absolute concept of social sustainability (Kristoffersen et al. 2024). The human-centred social values assessed and included in the certification systems primarily fall within the five themes: thermal comfort, indoor air quality, acoustics, daylight and electric light, and human health, with only a limited number of socially focused criteria falling outside these five themes (Kristoffersen et al. 2024).

The approach used in building certification systems has, however, several limitations and challenges. One of these is the checklist-like method applied in the systems where criteria are evaluated independently of each other based on material from the planning and construction stage of the building. This approach might lead to "point hunting", where criteria are evaluated and fulfilled based on the points they reward and not the value they add to the finished building and the building users' experience. An example of this is that a building may technically meet specified criteria intended to increase or ensure visual comfort. Still, without considering the building's specific use and users, the occupant experience might remain unsatisfactory or directly unpleasant, or the intended social value will simply not be present in the final building. A further challenge is that the certification systems approach assesses criteria and values related to each of the three pillars of sustainability (environmental, economic and social sustainability (Purvis et al. 2019)) separately, which can lead to taking actions to increase one aspect of

sustainability might negatively impact other unilluminated or unassessed aspects, therefore contrasting the understanding of sustainability as a holistic concept. Additionally, the rigid structure of the building certification systems means that the same standards and the same or similar criteria are applied across a range of building types and user groups, even though the users' needs can vary to a large degree.

In our recent research work (Kristoffersen et al. 2024), we have elaborated that the values assessed in the certification systems are related to some aspects of social sustainability referred to in the academic literature (as presented in Table 2) but that they are nowhere close to encompassing them all, or even a majority of them. Relating the aspects of social sustainability in Table 2 to the three levels of social values in Figure 4 shows that the aspects span all three levels. The use of the aspects to articulate specific focus points in creating social value highlights the connection between the concepts of social values, aspects of social sustainability, and the overarching concepts of sustainability and social sustainability.

Aspect	Aspect
Acceptance	Justice / fairness / equality / equity / ethics
Accessibility / inclusive design / Universal Design / Ergonomics	Knowledge and skill sharing
Affordability / economic accessibility	Land ownership
Basic human needs	Liveability
Basic human rights	People-centred / human-centred
Community resilience	Privacy
Creativity	Quality of life
Demographics	Representation / influence / democracy / participation
Economic security	Safety (accidents, harm)
Economy	Security (crime)
Education	Self-realisation
Effectivity / productivity	Services and facilities (available function in area / mixed use)
Engagement / engaging the local community	Social change
Environment	Social infrastructure
Flexibility	Social need

Health of people	Social networks / connections / interactions / social capital
Human dignity	Urban compactness / density of people (spatial development)
Human physical comfort (e.g. Air quality, indoor environment, noise, sound)	Visual connections between areas
Identity (culture) / sense of place / sense of belonging/heritage	Well fare / Wellness
Income	Wellbeing
Job opportunities/employment opportunities	Workers rights / Work conditions
Job security / stability	

Table 2: Aspects of social sustainability identified across the academic literature (Kristoffersen et al. 2024)

Developing and applying non-digital or digital tools can help project stakeholders, especially design teams, create and assess the variety of the different values listed in Table 1. In this regard, based on our recent research findings and our contribution to the PROBONO project, we (AU) are pursuing to develop and operationalise the following non-digital and digital tools:

a) SEEDS: Socio-Environmental Early-stage Decision Support

SEEDS is developed to provide the early design stakeholders with the ability to assess and communicate the impacts associated with including social intents in a building design project by illuminating the environmental, economic, and social impacts based on an evidence-based basis, building upon simple logical reasoning. The use of SEEDS in the planning of new projects allows building design stakeholders to perform a risk assessment of impacts across each of the three pillars, which will allow the design stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding the consequences of their choices and, therefore limit the risk of negatively impacting one or multiple aspects of sustainability when having an intention of increasing a perceived social value in a building (Kristoffersen et al. 2025).

b) ProBIM: Human-centered BIM

ProBIM is a BIM-based decision-support software tool that integrates as-designed social values directly in the BIM (Building Information Modelling) model. This allows *design arguments* about intended social values to be automatically checked and verified throughout a building's lifetime. The development includes three stages: 1) Formalizing architects' design intentions and the corresponding affected social values as well as the relationship between these social values and

building objects, 2) Extending the current industry foundation classes (IFC) in the BIMs standards to capture social values, design intentions and spatial artefacts, and 3) Developing and implementing a decision support software solution to provide an assessment methodology of social criteria in buildings. (Zayed et al. 2024)

3.2 GBN maturity and the use of ISO 37100

3.2.1 Measuring the GBN maturity

In other deliverables (D1.2, D9.8), we have proposed to measure the maturity of a GBN using two angles: the first, about assessing the **GBN organization maturity** in terms of GBN development capabilities, and the second in terms of the **maturity of the GBN programme**, that is, measuring the alignment of its different projects to its objectives, and how they contribute to the different communities services (education, mobility, ...) while considering ESG considerations.

- The organization component utilizes the ISO 37107 “Maturity Model for Smart Sustainable Communities” (MMSSC – see Figure 5) (ISO 2019), which is also presented in deliverable D1.2, section 3.2. This standardized framework provides a top-level maturity model for smart sustainable communities. It can be used for self-assessment by communities to evaluate how mature they are in adopting good practices for sustainable and smart-enabled development. The model helps communities identify their strengths and weaknesses, and guides them towards relevant international standards and guidance. By leveraging this established framework, GBNs can assess their maturity in a standardized manner that allows for comparison with other communities.
- The programme component also uses the ISO 37100 series, more specifically the ISO 37101 standard “Management system for sustainable development — Requirements with guidance for use” (ISO 2016), to enable a cross-analysis of GBN strategies, programmes, projects, plans, and services against the six sustainability / ESG purposes and twelve areas of actions. This ensures that all actions contribute to wider ESG objectives (see for example for the Aarhus living lab, Figure 6).

The six sustainability purposes are the following ones: (a) attractiveness, (b) preservation and improvement of the environment, (c) resilience, (d) responsible resource use, (e) social

cohesion, and (f) well-being. These purposes represent the overarching goals that sustainable communities should strive to achieve, from governance structures and educational initiatives to economic considerations and environmental protection. Along with the 12 areas of action, which include Governance issues, they are designed to be comprehensive, addressing social, economic, and environmental aspects of sustainability.

Figure 5: Overview of the ISO37107 MMSSC structure (ISO 2019)

The use of the internationally recognized standard ISO37101 series enables a complete review of a GBN maturity, both on what it intends to do and how it achieves its own targets while delivering on its ESG promises, but also allows, as part of an ISO series for Management Systems, a review of the GBN delivery bodies in terms of delivery capability, and possible way forward to improve.

The ISO37101 series of standards is now widely used as part of a certification system for organisations wishing to obtain certification in relation to management systems for sustainable communities (which includes GBN). The MMSSC maturity model is one of the solutions to obtain a vision of the maturity level of GBN to show the progress of human, technical and process capabilities to achieve sustainable communities. It should be considered by communities or GBNs that want to further develop their management systems to become GBNs. The Programme Maturity Tool, which places a particular emphasis on alignment between the vision and the project programme, should also be used early enough in the process to help stakeholders understand visually and according to an internationally proven framework what their vision and strategy is on the one hand, and how ongoing and planned activities contribute to this strategy on the other.

Figure 6: Comparing AAR UC (circles) to vision (stars). Size corresponds to the relative importance on a likert scale (from D1.2) (Source: PROBONO)

Moreover, we are developing a “Placemaking Fresk”, which corresponds to a “Climate Fresk” adapted to GBNs using this standard approach to ESG. This takes the form of a workshop, being assessed at the time of this report, which operationalises the concept of the programme component, and provides both an overview of the framework structure, and results in a first visual representation of the alignment between the GBN Vision and Activities, opening

discussions for better alignment. An early version was tested in practice with the Aarhus Living Lab, who said:

"It helped us to assess where we stand now and where we are heading to when the aim is working with as well as maturing on a GBN concept and in which way our activities are contributing to advance it further. In fact, after using the tool, one very interesting discovery for us was about the need to review and find a better alignment between our current individual activities (in the framework of the PROBONO project) and what we had earlier defined and elaborated on the scope or vision of our AU LL. This also gave us a heads up related to the impact of our activities (in PROBONO) and a lot of other activities that are under development within the LLs [locations in parallel to the] PROBONO project."

3.2.2 PROBONO Impacts and KPIs and their association with ISO 37100

PROBONO provides a framework that connects technologies and solutions, their deployment to the Living Labs for validation and testing and their assessment and relevant KPIs as key contributors to the PROBONO impacts through a clear, structured approach which is covered in WP6 and has been described in the deliverables D6.1 and D6.2 mainly while D6.3 defines the Living Labs KPI baselines.

Therefore, the technologies relate directly to quantitative impacts (e.g. energy savings in GWh, investment amounts in MEUR) relating to Environmental, Technical and Social goals. Each of these impacts then can be linked to align with specific goals from the ISO 37101 framework. The introduction of ISO 37101 as the means to align PROBONO with broader sustainability goals, ensures that its impacts become part of a holistic, integrated approach to building more sustainable, resilient, and cohesive communities.

The ISO 37101 involves the following six (6) sustainability goals: (a) Attractiveness, (b) Preservation and Improvement of Environment, (c) Resilience, (d) Responsible Resource Use, (e) Social Cohesion, (f) Well-being, and the following directions for sustainable initiatives: (1) Governance, Empowerment and Engagement, (2) Education and Capacity Building, (3) Innovation, Creativity and Research, (4) Health and Care in the Community, (5) Culture and Community Identity, (6) Living Together, Interdependence and Mutuality, (7) Economy and Sustainable Production and Consumption, (8) Living and Working Environment, (9) Safety and Security, (10) Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, (11) Community and Smart Infrastructures and (12) Mobility.

Table 3 shows a mapping of the Madrid Living Lab innovations, per Impact category with their expected outcome, and their ISO 37101 relevance.

PROBONO Impact	Relevant Technology	ISO 37101 Sustainability Principle	Expected Outcome
1. Primary energy savings triggered by the project (GWh/year)	Second Life Batteries DT-DHC network DT- Island effect Geothermal H-Pump Geothermal DHC Net.	Responsible Resource Use, Preservation & Improvement of Environment	Significant reduction in energy consumption due to optimized energy systems, leading to primary energy savings.
2. Investments in sustainable energy triggered by the project (million Euro)	DT-DHC network DT-reduce Env. Im DT- Island effect Geothermal H-Pump Geothermal DHC Net.	Economy and Sustainable Production & Consumption, Attractiveness	Attracting investments through innovative energy solutions and cost-effective designs.
3. Demonstration sites beyond nearly-zero energy building performance	Low Carbon concrete Low Carbon Asphalt Second Life Batteries Material movements Demolition Models DT-DHC network DT-reduce Env. Imp. DT- Island effect Geothermal H-Pump Geothermal DHC Net.	Innovation, Creativity, and Research, Preservation & Improvement of Environment	Exceed nearly-zero energy standards, showcasing the potential for high-performance buildings.
4. High energy performance (nearly zero-energy or positive-energy buildings)	Second Life Batteries DT-DHC network DT- Island effect Geothermal H-Pump Geothermal DHC Net.	Living and Working Environment, Resilience	High performance construction (zero or positive energy) meeting EU standards, reducing operational energy costs.
5. Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions towards zero (tCO ₂ -eq/year)	Second Life Batteries Material movements DT-DHC network DT-reduce Env. Imp. DT- Island effect Geothermal H-Pump Geothermal DHC Net.	Preservation & Improvement of Environment, Responsible Resource Use	A significant reduction in CO ₂ emissions due to renewable energy integration and energy-efficient systems.

6. Reduction of embodied energy in buildings by 50%	Low Carbon concrete Low Carbon Asphalt Material movements Demolition Models DT-reduce Env. Imp. DT- Island effect	Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, Preservation & Improvement of Environment	Reducing energy consumption and carbon footprint during production, construction, and operation of buildings.
7. Reduction of air pollutants towards zero (kg/year)	Second Life Batteries DT-DHC network DT-reduce Env. Imp. DT- Island effect Geothermal H-Pump Geothermal DHC Net.	Preservation & Improvement of Environment, Health and Care in the Community	Air pollution reduction via cleaner energy solutions, contributing to healthier living environments.
8. High potential for replicability using new/innovation clusters	Second Life Batteries Material movements Demolition Models DT-DHC network DT-reduce Env. Imp. DT- Island effect Geothermal H-Pump Geothermal DHC Net.	Innovation, Creativity, and Research, Economy and Sustainable Production & Consumption	High potential for replicating energy-efficient solutions in other regions, showcasing scalability and economic opportunity.
9. Shortened construction/retrofitting time and cost by at least 30%	Material movements Demolition Models DT-DHC network DT-reduce Env. Imp.	Economy and Sustainable Production & Consumption, Living and Working Environment	Reduction in time and costs for construction and retrofitting projects, improving social affordability and market uptake.
10. Improved final indoor environment quality by at least 30%	Second Life Batteries Material movements DT-reduce Env. Imp. DT- Island effect Geothermal H-Pump Geothermal DHC Net.	Health and Care in the Community, Well-being	Improved indoor air quality and comfort through energy-efficient building designs, increasing user satisfaction.

Table 3: Mapping PROBONO KPIs to ISO137101

3.3 Climate change adaptation and resilience measures

The integration of climate adaptation and resilience measures is an inherent step in the planning, implementation, and operation of sustainable and resilient GBNs (see also deliverable D1.2). According to the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, resilience is the ability of a system, community, or society exposed to hazards to resist, absorb, accommodate to, and recover from the effects of a hazard in a timely and efficient manner (United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction). This includes preserving and restoring its essential basic structure and functions. In recent decades, society has faced numerous hazards, including climate change, demographic imbalances, migration pressures, and pandemics (see also Figure 7).

Climate hazards, such as extreme heat, droughts, wildfires, flooding, sea level rise, and storms, are becoming more intense, longer, and more frequent. GBNs could be exposed to any of these hazards, making it necessary to implement adaptation measures to reduce their vulnerability and improve their capacity to navigate future shocks. Within the climate change framework, the IPCC defined vulnerability as “the degree to which a system is susceptible to, or unable to cope with, adverse effects of climate change, including climate variability and extreme” (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change 2012). In this context, the vulnerability of an asset or a GBN is a function of its sensitivity to be affected, either adversely or beneficially, by climate variability or change; and the adaptive capacity to adjust to climate change impacts, to moderate potential damage, to take advantage of opportunities, or to cope with consequences.

Figure 7 Climate risk components (European Environmental Agency and Climate ADAPT)

To address this challenge, the integration of climate adaptation measures of GBN should align with national policies and the European Commission’s resilience objectives (European Commission 2020). The latter includes achieving long-term structural change in a fair and inclusive way while reaching climate mitigation and adaptation goals, thereby enhancing both green and socio-economic resilience.

- **Climate adaptation and resilience measures for GBNs**

According to the UN, adaptation refers to adjustments or changes in processes, practices (operational), and structures (physical) to moderate potential damages or to benefit from opportunities associated with climate change (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change). In the specific framework of GBNs, the first step is to evaluate its current exposure to different climate hazards based on their location, as well as the capability and vulnerability to face the risk. Based on the potential impacts and damages identified, a comprehensive adaptation plan can be developed. This plan should include both structural and practice-based measures to enhance resilience and reduce vulnerability to climate hazards. Some of these measures are as follows:

Structural measures: Structural measures involve physical changes or additions to the built environment. These include:

- **Robust Building Design:** Constructing buildings to withstand extreme weather events, such as high winds or heavy rainfall. This involves using durable materials and designing buildings to minimize damage during disasters.
- **Structural Reinforcement:** Installing materials to reinforce buildings, such as stronger roofing materials, storm shutters, and impact-resistant windows. These improvements help buildings withstand extreme weather conditions.
- **Green Infrastructure:** Implementing green roofs, walls, and urban forests to reduce urban heat islands, improve air quality, and manage stormwater. These features help absorb rainwater, reduce runoff, and provide cooling effects.
- **Water Management:** Using permeable pavements, rain gardens, and retention basins to handle increased rainfall and prevent flooding. These systems allow water to infiltrate the ground, reducing the risk of surface flooding and recharging groundwater supplies.
- **Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy:** Enhancing building insulation, using energy-efficient appliances, and integrating renewable energy sources like solar panels. These measures reduce energy consumption, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and increase the resilience of energy supply systems.
- **Regular Maintenance Practices:** Implementing regular maintenance schedules to ensure that all structural components are in good condition. This includes inspecting and repairing roofs, walls, and foundations to prevent damage from climate hazards.

Practice-based measures: Practice-based measures involve changes in operational procedures and community practices. These include:

- Disaster Preparedness: Developing emergency response plans and community awareness programs. This includes training residents on how to respond to extreme weather events and establishing communication networks for timely information dissemination.
- Redundancy Systems: Ensuring backup power and water supply systems are in place. This includes installing generators, water storage tanks, and alternative energy sources to maintain essential services during disruptions.

By integrating these structural and practice-based measures from the planning stage, GBNs can enhance their resilience to climate change, reduce vulnerability to hazards, and improve their capacity to recover from adverse climate events. This planning requires an holistic approach including technological, social and ecological factors of the GBN and their interactions, engagement of stakeholders, as well as monitoring and evaluation measures to assess the effectiveness of adaptation and resilience strategies and make adjustments as needed (Buildings Performance Institute Europe 2024).

3.4 Enhancing biodiversity

3.4.1 Green roofs and biodiversity

Green roofs are seen as an important element of the strategy towards mitigating the negative effects of urbanization and climate change (see also deliverable D1.5). There has been an increase in green roof studies and how different solutions are associated with ecosystem services, sustainability and biodiversity. In particular, research evidence shows that green roofs are linked with a wide range of environmental, social and economic benefits when compared with conventional types of roofs (Shafique et al. 2018). Green roof technology is often considered to be of added value with respect to reducing energy consumption as well as minimizing the effects of heavy rainfalls and the urban heat island phenomenon. Moreover, green roof applications are often found to be an appropriate solution to deal with noise pollution (Vijayaraghavan 2016) and create an natural aesthetic result which provides opportunities for outdoor recreation activities. Green roofs are broadly characterised between intensive and extensive types with the second ones being the dominant solution due to the lower installation

and maintenance requirements. The basic structural difference between these types has to do with the substrate depth which normally exceeds 20 cm in IGR and is equal to or lower than 15 cm in EGR (Saadatian et al. 2013). There is a notable difference between the applicability of EGR versus IGR which is believed to be due to the second's higher structural, maintenance requirements and higher installation costs. Hybrid green roof concepts are emerging to include solutions integrating PVs and green roofs, green roofs together with vertical elements i.e. green walls or a combination of water-based (often called blue) and green spaces. A thorough overview of key practical considerations and benefits regarding green roof design and construction is found in (Vijayaraghavan 2016).

In terms of their social benefits such as improvement of human health and well-being, habitat restoration and biodiversity enhancement (Shafique et al. 2018; Peng and Jim 2013; MacIvor and Lundholm 2011; Francis and Lorimer 2011), green roofs are considered to play a positive role, however quantification of their effect is not an easy task.

A number of research activities connecting green roofs to biodiversity can be found in (URBANhabitats 2006) ranging from long term vegetation research, urban wildlife and birds habitat design, invertebrates, etc. In addition, arthropod diversity the ecological processes of a green roof in a semi-rural area of Argentina is investigated in (Sánchez Domínguez et al. 2020). An analysis of whether intensive green roofs create environmental conditions comparable to those of adjacent urban ground-level habitats is conducted in (MacIvor and Lundholm 2011). Evidence demonstrates that a wide variety of insects including uncommon species find favourable conditions in green roofs therefore supporting the idea that green roofs can support biodiversity in the urban space. Experimental analysis was also conducted in (Droz et al. 2021), to analyse semi-intensive green roof design parameters versus performance according to criteria including planted vegetation, weeds, soil carbon and stormwater runoff. Moreover, the role of green roofs in the preservation of wildlife in the dense urban environment has been studied in (Parkins and Clark 2015). Results associated the levels of bat activity found to be higher over green roofs compared to conventional roofs.

3.4.2 Biodiversity in the different stages of project development

Measures to integrate biodiversity enhancement in new construction and renovation projects in general and GBNs in particular must be implemented in all phases of project development (see also deliverable D1.1). The following are the elements developed by the International Biodiversity & Real Estate Council (IBPC) as part of the BiodiverCity® Construction Standard.

Design: Commit to displaying ambition for biodiversity, create a biodiversity policy akin to the architectural intent, green the building and its surroundings, and invite architects and designers to incorporate these issues.

Construction: Commit to a construction site that respects biodiversity, particularly soil and sensitive species when present, and ensure the preservation of this biodiversity.

Operation: Implement measures to ensure the durability of the actions by factoring in these conditions during design and providing resources for the continuity of the measures.

This also implies a commitment from the project leaders to make this subject a key issue and to involve all partners in the project management process continuously throughout all phases of the project.

3.4.2.1 Actions to be Implemented Prior to Project Design to Preserve the Site's Ecological Potential

Biodiversity is complex and often misunderstood, even in cities. The city's residents and operators are usually unaware of the manifestations of its presence. To uncover it, the project owner must commit to understanding, preserving, and managing it.

The approach requires an in-depth or suitable knowledge of local ecological elements (habitats, native and introduced species, often neglected in the real estate or construction sectors) and an initiation into their significance, organization, and functionality.

Understanding GBNs's Ecosystems and Its Surroundings

Regarding biodiversity, knowing and promoting awareness is already a significant part of action and protection efforts. The foundation of all action is knowledge: to act, one must know what they are dealing with.

This initial step in the field of ecology involves carrying out naturalist inventories, tailored to the program and the project on the site and its immediate surroundings (nature does not recognize property boundaries). This commitment to knowledge goes beyond ownership and demonstrates an involvement in the neighbourhood.

A specific ecological study should include an initial site diagnosis, describing natural habitats (identification and description) and associated communities of flora and fauna, as well as the site's context, strengths, and ecological constraints. Inventories should be conducted before any work commences and during optimal times for the species in question. The immediate surroundings of the parcel should also be considered.

Promoting biodiversity in a construction project is not only about creating new habitats but also about planning for the preservation of existing ones:

- Preserving valuable habitats as much as possible: Identify the vegetation cover to be preserved due to habitat maturity, importance for resilience, and adaptation.
- Preserving existing flora and fauna: Conduct inventories by naturalists, ecologists of existing flora and fauna to identify heritage species as well as common flora and fauna.
- Soil preservation: Soil composition and specificities are critical functional components of ecosystems (recycling, water reserve, seed bank, etc.). Moreover, the top layers of the soil are living ecotones harboring a significant micro-biodiversity (earthworms, insects, crustaceans). The goal is a technical, economic, and ecological optimization to preserve/reuse existing soils, diversify substrates, and promote biodiversity by providing varied useful biotopes. Therefore, the soil composition should be known to facilitate reuse.

The understanding of the site's initial richness will inform choices in project design, operation, and management.

Considering the Parcel's Geography

Regional pedoclimatic differences, ecological history, and geographic evolution affect species selection and development, as well as the evolution of a natural area or urban nature. Knowledge of the biogeographic context will define criteria for the project and future developments.

Informing Project Stakeholders and Future Users About the Site's Initial Richness and Associated Challenges to Explain Design Choices

The goal is to inform and raise awareness among interested parties about the commitment to biodiversity based on the results of the ecologist's study and site inventories. This information must be shared with the project's technical teams (architect, project manager, landscape architect, etc.) and will enable the incorporation of adapted challenges during the design phase. Identifying these challenges (points of interest, potential for enhancement, constraints) should allow for defining design details and biodiversity-supporting measures adapted to the site's ecology (preservation / conservation / regeneration measures) in the design phase. Actions should be justified based on knowledge of the site, its immediate surroundings, and how the project will synchronize with them.

3.4.2.2 Actions Aimed at Project Design for Renovation or Construction

Adding New Skills to the Project Team

Studying fauna, flora, and urban ecosystems requires specific skills in scientific ecology as applied to the construction and real estate fields.

- *Ecologist:* The project owner should be able to enlist a qualified individual on these topics for the entire duration of the project—a professional in ecology who will provide advice and expertise on biodiversity themes. This professional can define and justify the scope of the investigations proposed to ensure the quality of the necessary measures for biodiversity enhancement (during the site inventory, as well as during design and operation), and train teams throughout the project. To ensure the proper application of biodiversity measures across the project, it will also be essential to ensure the engagement of partners, from the design / construction team to future tenants and operators. Choosing a design / construction team committed to biodiversity themes ensures that this topic is addressed upstream and during construction. To sustain actions after project completion, the project owner should ensure that project partners commit to and continue the initial objectives in favor of biodiversity.
- *Landscape Architect:* Additional expertise must collaborate with the ecologist and the project leader. Collaborative work between the ecologist and the landscape architect is essential.

Incorporating Local Issues and Ecological Continuities into the Project

- *Meeting local objectives:* The project should comply with local biodiversity conservation goals and align with the city's associated urban planning goals (local biodiversity plans, nature education initiatives, citizen science activities, and communication about local biodiversity). The project should seek synergy by identifying expectations and planning exchanges with local representatives.
- *Integrating into the local ecological network and regional biological frameworks:* The project will be situated within an existing environment of natural reservoirs, ecological corridors, buffer zones, and natural barriers. An ecological network includes three basic elements: nodal zones (vital zones rich in biodiversity where individuals can complete their life cycle), corridors (connections between nodal zones), and buffer zones (protecting nodal zones and corridors from external influences). Ecological continuity combines biodiversity reservoirs and ecological corridors.

For the GBNs, understanding and integrating into this local biological system based on identifying and describing ecological reservoirs will be essential. Integration involves implementing arrangements (nature frameworks, green frameworks) whose nature and quality favor local reservoirs (habitat types, species, arrangement layouts, continuities).

- *Enhancing hygrophilous continuity:* Ecological corridors are made up of vegetated terrestrial continuities and aquatic and wetland continuities. The mineral and artificial nature of the urban environment creates a heavily disrupted setting for hygrophilous continuities due to impermeable soils and the challenging infiltration of water. Runoff transports polluted water. Additionally, aquatic and wetland corridors, when they exist, are rarely treated as complete ecosystems (e.g., mineralized or covered systems).

Identify and Integrate the Project's Ecological Potential (Before-After and Variants)

Upfront, the client's requests and requirements, as well as the documents provided with the program, should guide the architectural and landscaping approach of the project in favor of biodiversity:

- *Anticipate the project's relative impact on its environment and reduce the ecological impact of the site's urbanization:* The project is evaluated in relation to its initial state (see above). A before/after comparison of the site's green surface area versus the surrounding area's green surface area must then be conducted. The goal is to highlight the efforts to increase vegetation and to penalize operations that remove the last green elements from the site. This analysis can be done with a mapping tool that estimates the total green areas before and after.
- *Optimize the project approach:* Identify negative and positive ecological impacts (regeneration) in relation to site constraints and initial conditions and establish all necessary responses to address them.
- *Assess the project's ecological potential:* A before-and-after project evaluation may be conducted using the Guy Berthoud method developed by IPBC.

Develop a "Biodiversity Approach" throughout the GBN

For each project, ecological conditions differ depending on the location (on the edge of a green belt or in dense urban areas). In all these cases, there may exist site-specific biodiversity, to be taken as a reference context, and to be proposed to architects as a key element of architectural intention.

- *Develop an architectural approach focused on biodiversity:* Encourage architects and project managers to innovate by integrating living elements. The aim is to invite a new generation of buildings, with architectural approaches dedicated to biodiversity or using living elements in architecture: green innovations, reconstituted ecosystems on rooftops or buildings, original aesthetics with dominant nature...
- *Define and promote target animal species for the project:* Depending on the context and knowledge of the site, target species are defined (notably animals). The target species must be ecologically coherent. The project will establish recommendations in their favor.
- *Manage rainwater, preserve open soil:* In urban environments, a major issue is soil impermeability due to mineralization. Natural spaces and elements play a role in natural water regulation on the parcel and in the area by allowing water infiltration (permeable spaces). Rooftop terraces, by absorbing rainwater, will thus prevent rapid runoff into networks and reduce their flow: a buffering role. This buffering role can also be played by exterior basins or other collection systems and natural hydric networks: swales and ditches. Finally, natural spaces contribute to air humidification through plant evapotranspiration, humidity also playing a role in cooling temperatures.
- *Green the building and its surroundings:* Greening the exterior compensates for the artificialization and mineralization of the site on which the project is built. The envelopes, parts of the building in direct contact with the external environment, provide an opportunity to create new vertical (vertical facades) and horizontal (roofs) biotopes. The project may address as many envelopes as possible to make them complete biotopes.
- *Develop the ecological capacity of useful biotopes in the constructed area or on the initial site:* Maximize the surface area of green spaces and useful biotopes on the building and its surroundings, regardless of their ecological quality here: green spaces, gardens, green spaces on rooftops, green walls, green terraces, and seek to diversify useful biotopes and greening methods for buildings: semi-permeable zones, green spaces on rooftops, vertical greening, or any other spaces and surfaces that can be dedicated to flora and fauna.
- *Preserve pre-existing environmental amenities on the site and its surroundings, and create new ones:* Environmental amenities offer positive perceptions and particular appeal to the site for project users. The primary objective was the identification and

preservation of existing amenities. Ecology-related amenities initially exist independently of the project and have considerable benefits (landscape quality, plant maturity). First, these are to be identified to allow, second, their safeguarding, preservation, and protection in the project and during construction. Amenities irreparably impacted by construction should be subject to restoration actions. New amenities can be created (common nature space, notable tree, ornamental pond).

- *Integrate nature-provided services for the adaptation and resilience of the project:* In urban environments, comfort is also about temperatures, shading, and the heat island effect caused by urban density and mineralization. Installations on buildings (e.g., green terraces), around buildings (e.g., water features, trees close to buildings, vegetative barriers to manage wind) incorporate these adaptation challenges.

Urban climates are also impacted by the heat island effect (localized temperature increases) due to urban density and mineralization. Ecological measures are taken to limit this effect and contribute locally to climate regulation within and around the building. Plants, consuming CO₂ and releasing oxygen, play a role in climate regulation. They cool the air (through shading and moisture) and insulate buildings from external conditions (vegetative facade protection in summer). Efforts will also be made to limit solar reflection: shaded and vegetated spaces to reduce heat reflection on buildings and occupied outdoor spaces, as well as green roofs and/or parking lots.

- *Choose a plant palette adapted to the biogeographic context and reintroduce local species:* For sustainability, in choosing the plant palette, the project must consider the climate (plant species and drought tolerance, materials and frost resistance, etc.) and the available resources for plant care and maintenance (financial, human, type of energy, etc.).
- *Reduce the building's impact on local ecosystems and biological balances:* The existing or planned building may have harmful effects on wildlife, which must be identified to mitigate associated risks. Firstly, facades can be particularly dangerous when they reflect the sky or vegetation, making it difficult for birds to discern the building. Certain architectural features and arrangements especially increase collision risks: reflective glass surfaces, glass corners creating double transparency, and trees near glass surfaces. To limit these risks, visual barriers will be created to fragment reflections of vegetation and sky on glass surfaces. Urban lighting, in general, disrupts the biological cycles of animal and plant species by altering their perception of natural daily light cycles. It

affects species' reproduction, photosynthesis, and rest cycles. Light pollution will be reduced, and lighting can be adapted (e.g., downward lighting, reduced light intensity, shorter lighting duration in vegetated areas). Other direct or indirect impacts may exist and should be minimized: deadly cavities (e.g., open, hollow poles). These structures often trap birds and are usually fatal.

- *Provide easy access to natural spaces*: Green spaces at the foot of buildings are ideal for promoting user access to nature, enabling regular daily contact. These directly accessible spaces complement access to large green spaces in the area or nearby public gardens. Establishing a natural space within the project is the primary guarantee of access for users. For physical access, the green space must be communal and accessible to all.

3.4.2.3 Actions for Project Implementation and Long-Term Monitoring

- *Implement commitments in market and work documents*: This step involves preparing for the operational implementation (by contractors) of the arrangements, techniques, and various systems in favor of the project's biodiversity, by anticipating the quality of their execution and ensuring their effectiveness (ecological potential, amenities, ecosystem services).

Since biodiversity relies on new techniques and equipment (generally not well-mastered by construction companies), it is important to technically explain and specify the biodiversity measures in execution documents and procedures (technical specifications, plans, model material sheets, etc.). These works and operations must be assigned to qualified individuals whose involvement will be scheduled throughout the construction phases (division of work). In general, it is advisable to separate green space and planting interventions from other external works (roads and utility networks) to ensure specific expertise, quality guarantees, and to achieve the intended objectives.

- *Preserve the site during the construction phase*: Construction is a critical time for the project in relation to the initial environment, as it is the phase when the site undergoes the most significant changes (destruction of individual plants and existing natural habitats; disturbances and disruptions; soil degradation; indirect impacts). The most sensitive phases include preparatory work: deforestation/clearing, cleaning/demolition, and earthworks. For example, it is essential to identify refuge zones during construction, protect trees, define appropriate intervention dates, and limit disturbances.

The approach must be incorporated into contractual documents and various construction documents, and biodiversity objectives should be communicated and explained to the construction teams.

- *Protect preserved natural elements and those near the site during construction:* To reduce permanent ecological impacts, the priority is to preserve natural elements where they exist and when the project can maintain them.

On-site and in the surrounding areas, natural elements must be protected during construction: trees, hedges, groves, wetlands (swales, ponds, streams), nests, old stone walls, meadow patches, etc.

- *Maintain investment capacity at the realization and monitoring levels despite project changes:* The project owner must commit to designating a biodiversity representative for the operational phase to continue the initial objectives once the building is delivered.
- *Consider long-term preservation challenges:* To ensure the continuity of the approach beyond delivery, the site's management and maintenance program will be ecologically focused on the initial biodiversity objectives. Actions will aim for long-term ecological management in partnership with users and continuous improvement of practices (quality approach).

The ecological maintenance program will aim to uphold the project's ecological objectives, establishing an ambition, framework, and methodology to ensure the long-term ecological quality of the site's spaces.

- *Enable and even encourage collective activities:* In addition to fostering connections between residents and building users, collective activities provide relaxation and shared experiences, essential for well-being and quality of life. Organizing various nature-related workshops aims to combine biodiversity awareness with fostering a relationship between humans and their environment.

3.4.3 Highly Evaporative Green Roofs

In PROBONO, highly evaporative green roofs (HEGR) are demonstrated as a possible technology that increases biodiversity. When using HEGR, a distinction must be made between its thermal and other effects on the interior of the building and on the building's surroundings.

On a previous collaboration between SOPREMA & TIPEE, a model has been developed to evaluate indoor and outdoor HEGR effects. A green roof model was therefore developed and integrated into TRNSYS 18 (Djedjig et al. 2012; Thermal Energy System Specialists, LLC 2024). With the model, the impact of the complete green roof system on the roof heat fluxes to the building and the impact on Heat Urban Island effect via the Latent Heat Flux from the roof to the air above the roof can be simulated.

Energy needs will be calculated in kWh/m²/year. In order to obtain the corresponding electrical consumption, the conversion efficiencies of the energy systems need to be included. In summary, the interface between the green roof model and the TRNSYS model occurs at the roof boundary condition, where the roof temperature is set to that of the bottom of the substrate as presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Green roof model

As an example, for the Living Lab Prague one model without a green roof (left) and one with a green roof (right) to evaluate the impact (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: 3D model of the Prague LL building with (right) and without (left) green roof

Model calculations show that the temperature of the roof surface without a green roof can reach up to 40°C during the day in summer, which is much higher than the ambient temperature. With a green roof, on the other hand, it remains below 25 °C, which also has a positive effect on the lifespan, among other things. This can be explained by the combined effects of water evaporation in the plants and the additional thermal inertia of the substrate. At night, however, the temperature of the roof without a green roof drops to lower values due to the radiative cooling from the night sky.

In summary, the installation of a HEGR can provide more comfort in summer and savings on air conditioning, provided that the plants are sufficiently watered. Finally, it is important to remember that the installation of a HEGR reduces the heat load of heat transfer through conduction through the roof. This thermal load is only part of the total thermal loads due to air exchange, solar gains, internal gains, etc. In addition, if the roof is well insulated, the effect of a HEGR on air conditioning consumption is reduced.

4 Additional metrics for GBN development

4.1 Integration of the ESG perspective in GBN development

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) elements are crucial for Green Building Neighbourhood development as they provide a comprehensive framework for sustainable and responsible urban planning. The environmental aspect of ESG aligns closely with the core principles of GBNs, focusing on energy efficiency, renewable energy integration, waste

reduction, and preservation of natural resources. This ensures that GBNs are designed and operated in a way that minimizes their ecological footprint and contributes positively to climate change mitigation efforts.

The social and governance components of ESG are equally important in GBN development. They emphasize the creation of inclusive, equitable, and well-managed communities that prioritize the well-being of residents. This includes considerations such as affordable housing, accessible public spaces, community engagement in decision-making processes, and the provision of essential services. By incorporating these ESG elements, GBNs can foster social cohesion, improve quality of life, and ensure long-term sustainability beyond just environmental considerations.

The use of the ISO 37101 series can significantly aid in developing GBNs that align with ESG requirements. ISO 37101 provides a structured management system for sustainable development in communities, which inherently addresses many ESG concerns. The standard's framework, with its 12 areas of action and 6 sustainability purposes, offers a comprehensive approach that covers environmental, social, and governance aspects. For instance, areas of action such as "Governance, empowerment and engagement" directly address the governance aspect of ESG, while "Biodiversity and ecosystem services" aligns with environmental considerations.

Moreover, the iterative cross-analysis required by ISO 37101, where strategies and projects are evaluated against both the areas of action and sustainability purposes, ensures a holistic approach to GBN development. This process helps identify gaps in ESG performance and guides continuous improvement. The standard's emphasis on stakeholder engagement, performance evaluation, and continual improvement also aligns well with ESG principles of transparency and accountability. GBN developers can systematically address ESG criteria, enhance their sustainability performance, and potentially improve their attractiveness to ESG-focused investors and residents.

Various tools are available to assess the ESG perspective of GBNs. Mott MacDonald developed the **Moata ESG** solution for this purpose, which was originally intended to be used in the PROBONO LLs. However, this tool is no longer available since 2021/2022, while there still remains a brand "**Moata People and Planet**", this is not a tool but a proprietary, commercial consulting service supported by a digital solution (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: Example of Moata People and Planet dashboards

This solution uses data-driven insights to reveal and quantify the potential social and environmental impacts of various options for proposed large-scale infrastructure projects and investments. The advisory services combine available data with data on proposed investments in assets to assess social and environmental factors based on business priorities. It also draws on a proprietary library of indicators, in which metrics are regularly updated. Incorporating targeted sustainability factors into decision-making can help realize infrastructure's full potential – serving society and improving people's lives, livelihoods and the environment, as well as transforming communities and places by providing a decision support tool to map investments onto sustainability benefits, enhancing the bankability of selected options.

4.2 Integration of the investment conditions in GBN development

The increasing awareness of the construction sector's impact on climate change has driven the rise of GBNs. These projects prioritise ESG principles over purely financial returns, creating a need for innovative financing approaches (Eichholtz et al. 2013). This chapter explores the role of green finance as a suitable funding source for GBNs, examining various financing instruments that align with sustainable goals. It discusses how these financial tools—ranging from green bonds to EU-backed funds—support green building initiatives, addresses key challenges within the sector, and considers potential solutions. One can also learn from the part of the reviewed ISO standard series, in particular “ISO37116 Sustainable cities and communities — Disaster risk

finance — Principles and general requirements for financing ex-ante investment in risk reduction” (ISO 2024).

4.2.1 Description of what financing options are available for GBNs and how these can be used to develop GBNs

Green buildings and neighbourhoods are increasingly recognised as higher value assets than standard structures, based on their lower fiscal, regulatory and reputational risks (United Nations Environment Programme 2020). Additionally, they typically incur in a lower incremental cost, at typically 1 per cent of capital expenses, have lower long-term operating and maintenance cost, lower default rates, and smaller odds of becoming a stranded asset. As a result, minimising environmental impact is progressively associated with maximising returns and increasing returns on investment (United Nations Environment Programme 2020). Therefore, sustainable building investment is anticipated to be one of the largest investment opportunities of the next few years, estimated on \$24.7 trillion by 2030 (Likhachova et al. 2019).

How are green buildings normally financed? However, these innovative models are often financed by traditional financing models, which frequently misalign with the core elements of GBNs hindering their objectives and creating regulatory and practical constraints (Agliardi and Agliardi 2019). This had led to green finance being increasingly viewed as the most suitable source of funding for GBNs (Akomea-Frimpong et al. 2022).

What is green finance: Green Finance encompasses a broader scope than traditional finance, integrating climate and environmental protection goals such as pollution control, nature conservation and climate neutrality. Even though its origins trace back to the 1970, it gained momentum in 2010 with the creation of the Green Climate Fund, when 194 countries pledged financial aid to developing countries for climate change mitigation (Wang and Zhi 2016). Following the formulation of the SDGs, the adoption of the Paris Agreement and Sendai Framework for Risk Reduction, green finance was recognised as a key element in the fight against the triple planetary crisis: Biodiversity Loss, Climate Change, and Pollution (Adeyemi 2014). Green financial assets can be both public and private, and broadly include: Green bonds and loans (which fund new or existing eligible green projects with explicit environmental benefits); Green Funds (equity or debt financing platforms that support environmentally conscious businesses and organisations); green credits (such as green deposits, loans, mortgages, and project loans); green banks, and other forms of socially responsible investment (SRI) (Debrah et al. 2022; Sachs et al. 2019).

Green finance for Green buildings: While green finance and its impact on green buildings remains an under-researched area, leading to a lack of development and funding (Debrah et al. 2022), evidence suggests that green finance is the most suitable funding source for GBNs. Green finance not only provides substantial long-term capital for the design, construction, and management of GBNs, but also does so at lower risk (Szumilo and Fuerst 2015; Dikau and Volz 2018). In 2021, green finance for green buildings reached a global high of \$27 billion (International Finance Corporation 2023).

The main types of private finance identified as significantly fostering the development and construction of GBNs include the following:

Sustainable property funds: Also known as ESG property funds, these funds focus on real estate assets with sustainable, environmentally friendly and socially responsible characteristics. Allocating these funds often involves several steps, including an initial sustainability assessment, a plan for sustainability-focused upgrades, and measurable objectives aligned with national goals (European Bank for Reconstruction and Development 2021). In 2021, the first exchange-traded fund (ETF) for green buildings was introduced, tracking the Global Green Building Index (Dugo 2021). Furthermore, the EU Commission announced on their EU Action Plan on Sustainable Finance its intention to support the re-calibration of banks' capital requirements to invest in green buildings (Jones Day 2019).

Green bonds/loans: Unlike property funds, green bonds are typically secured by individual borrowers from lenders or supported by the green bond market, with prices influenced by supply and demand. Green bonds may take various forms, including financial and bank-related SDG bonds, non-financial corporate SDG bonds, municipal SDG bonds, sovereign bonds, and asset-backed SDG bonds (Larcker and Watts 2020). An example on their use is India's largest cement producer, Ultra Tech. In 2021, they issued a sustainability-linked bond tied to the compliance of the company's self-determined target of reducing their carbon emissions by 22 per cent by 2030. If the target was missed, the interest rate would rise by 75 basis points. It was launched in domestic and international capital markets, raising \$400 million (Susanta 2024).

Green Mortgages: Another key financial product driving green building investment, green mortgages offer homeowners preferential rates and terms for purchasing or renovating properties that meet environmental standards. These mortgages, often supported by European governments, encourage sustainable housing choices by making eco-friendly properties more affordable and reducing energy costs. For banks, green mortgages represent a lower-risk,

higher-return investment, as green-certified properties tend to yield long-term value and savings (Green and Wachter 2010).

Banks and the broader banking system remain essential players, providing customized financial options, such as specialized mortgages, home improvement loans, and green mortgages, with favorable terms. These instruments enable banks to diversify portfolios, reduce risk, and attract clients interested in sustainable property investments, fostering a lower-risk, higher-value asset base (Likhachova et al. 2019).

Public-Private Partnerships: In most cases, for optimal results in investing in GBNs, private finance should be complemented by public support. This can be achieved through a two-fold strategy:

Firstly, public advocacy, which includes setting ambitious national targets and taking specific actions, such as promoting expedited permitting processes. Secondly, economic policy and fiscal incentives, such as tax breaks, subsidies, and state-sponsored loans, can further encourage investment in green buildings (Likhachova et al. 2019). Collaboration between financial institutions and government bodies leads to Public-Private Partnership (PPP) products that are particularly effective for green building infrastructure, especially highlighting:

Bioclimatic (Green) Building Funds (GBFs): multi-stakeholder funds sponsored by the government and involving industry practitioners, financiers, and building users. These funds are designed to promote emissions reductions and address environmental challenges in the construction sector (Creamer 2015). An example is the GBFs launched in Australia in 2008 as part of the Clean Business Australia initiative, which provided a total of AUD 118.7 million and reduced over 285,000 tonnes of greenhouse gas emissions per annum (International Energy Agency 2017).

4.2.2 Accessing EU Green Finance for Green Building Projects

The European Union's Green Deal sets an ambitious goal for climate neutrality by 2050, directing significant funding to reduce emissions across key sectors, especially construction and energy (European Commission 2019). To achieve this, the EU has established a variety of financial instruments aimed specifically at "greening" buildings, including support for energy-efficient construction, renovations, and emissions reductions in the building sector. These include:

Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) 2021-2027 and NextGenerationEU (NGEU): The MFF and NGEU together provide substantial financial support, with a combined budget of EUR 2.018

trillion, aimed at driving the EU's transition toward a green and digital economy (European Commission 2021). Within this framework, significant resources are allocated to energy-efficient building renovations and sustainable infrastructure improvements, with grants and loans made available to member states for implementing green building projects, including retrofitting buildings to reduce emissions and enhance energy efficiency.

InvestEU: As a component of the MFF, InvestEU provides EUR 26.2 billion in guarantees to mobilise an estimated EUR 372 billion in public and private investments across four policy areas, including sustainable infrastructure and energy efficiency in buildings (European Investment Bank 2021). InvestEU's focus on green infrastructure supports projects that incorporate renewable energy systems into buildings, sustainable construction materials, and large-scale energy-saving upgrades, often in collaboration with the European Investment Bank (EIB).

Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF): The RRF, which makes up 90% of NextGenerationEU's budget, provides EUR 723.8 billion in grants and loans to assist EU countries with economic recovery aligned with climate objectives, with 37% of funds earmarked for green investments, especially building renovations (European Commission 2022). Member States submit Recovery and Resilience Plans (RRPs) detailing projects for financing, including residential and public building energy-efficient renovations and renewable energy system integrations.

Green Bonds: The EU has issued green bonds to fund projects aligned with the Green Deal, raising EUR 12 billion for sustainable investments under the NextGenerationEU program (European Commission 2021). Green bonds attract private capital and offer investors long-term, lower-risk opportunities focused on sustainable outcomes, including green building renovations and upgrades to meet energy standards.

The following, non-EU funds, play a key role within the EU scope:

European Energy Efficiency Fund (EEEF): The EEEF supports sustainable energy projects in the public sector by providing technical assistance, loans, equity investments, and grants (European Energy Efficiency Fund 2021). This fund supports municipalities and other public entities in implementing energy-efficient building projects, such as improved lighting, insulation, and heating systems, along with renewable energy integration.

European Investment Bank (EIB) Green Investments: The EIB is a key partner in the EU's green agenda, committing to direct 50% of its annual financing toward green investments by 2025 (European Investment Bank 2021). Through direct loans, intermediary financing, and investment

guarantees, the EIB supports retrofitting, urban development, and affordable green housing initiatives, often collaborating with InvestEU to amplify the scale of green building investments.

European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) Green Economy Transition (GET)

Plan: The EBRD supports green building finance across Europe through its GET plan, which focuses on aligning projects with international climate agreements and scaling investments across green sectors, including energy systems and green buildings. The EBRD provides resources such as training in energy management, sustainability certification, market analysis, and feasibility studies. Additionally, it supports large-scale public-private partnerships (PPP), leveraging technical assistance to bridge financing gaps and ensure the success of green building projects (European Bank for Reconstruction and Development 2021).

4.2.3 Challenges and Solutions in Financing Green Buildings

Despite robust financial support, several barriers continue to hinder the growth of green finance in the building sector. Issues such as fragmented markets, limited capacity, and conflicting incentives between private and public stakeholders pose challenges to accessing finance (European Bank for Reconstruction and Development 2021). (Akomea-Frimpong et al. 2022) also highlight confusion over green finance qualifications, limited awareness of long-term benefits, and high borrowing costs, particularly for SMEs in developing economies. Securing green finance certifications remains challenging due to evolving standards.

To address these barriers, solutions have emerged that can help make green finance more accessible and effective. These include standardising green finance assessments, developing cost-benefit analysis frameworks, and implementing performance measurement tools to demonstrate tangible benefits (Debrah et al. 2022). Additionally, public-private partnerships (PPP) facilitate cross-sector collaboration, scaling green building initiatives through shared resources. Another approach to enhancing sustainability in the sector is to green the construction supply chain itself. By improving sustainability practices at each stage—from material sourcing to waste management—the building industry can reduce its overall environmental impact and create a more cohesive approach to achieving climate goals.

As a conclusion, green finance provides essential support for GBNs, offering financing options that align with sustainability goals more effectively than traditional models. Various alternatives, such as green bonds, sustainable property funds, green mortgages, and public-private partnerships, have been explored as tools that can address and correctly deliver on the unique financial needs of GBNs. While challenges remain, these alternatives demonstrate the potential

of green finance to bridge funding gaps and advance sustainable practices in the construction and urbanism sectors, supporting both environmental impact reduction, social and governance goals, and uphold long-term financial stability.

4.2.4 A Comprehensive Look at Sustainable Supply Chain Finance

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) possess tremendous potential as drivers of green and inclusive growth, yet they often encounter barriers when seeking financing for sustainable practices. These challenges are not unlike those faced in developing GBNs would be expected to face, where sustainable objectives must be balanced with financial realities. In this context, SMEs serve as a valuable baseline for understanding the financial supply chain dynamics that are likely to shape the future of GBN development. This study explores how the financial mechanisms supporting SMEs can be applied to GBNs, specifically through Supply Chain Finance (SCF) models that encourage sustainability.

SCF has emerged as a promising solution to financing while fostering sustainable practices. Building on this concept, the study proposes the Sustainable Supply Chain Finance (SSCF) funds may be a part of the future solution to support the financial needs for a Green Building Neighbourhoods. These SSCF funds could be provide the needs in design to facilitate financing, mitigate greenwashing, enhance transparency, and bridge the gap in sustainable supply chain finance development. Successful examples of companies integrating SSCF into their operations demonstrate its transformative potential in promoting sustainability. Thus, SSCF funds represent a potential crucial step towards aligning financial practices with sustainability objectives and offer a structured pathway for both SMEs and GBNs, paving the way for a more resilient and sustainable future.

Climate change is one of the most pressing global challenges we face today. The realization that its potential consequences could have severe negative impacts on human civilization prompted pivotal actions beginning with the United Nations Conference on Environmental and Development in 1992, also known as the Rio Summit or Earth Summit. The objective of the Summit was to develop a comprehensive plan for global cooperation on environmental and development issues that would help achieve sustainable development throughout the 20th century (United Nations 1993). In 1994, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), an international environmental treaty, adopted at the Rio Summit, came into effect, with an aim to limit greenhouse gas emissions on a global scale (United Nations 1994).

Since 1995, countries that joined UNFCCC have met annually at the Conference of Parties (COP) to address climate change issues (United Nations 2024). An important milestone from COP's meetings is the Paris Agreement (PA) from 2015, where 196 nations adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and agreed to actions and investments toward a low-carbon, resilient, and sustainable future (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change 2015). The PA aimed to limit global temperature rise to well below two °C and strive for 1.5°C while also helping countries to address climate change by aligning financial flows with low greenhouse gas emissions and climate-resilient pathways (Calster and Reins, 2021). In response to the PA, International institutions like the European Union have also taken measures to encourage companies to integrate ESG factors into their operations, such as creating climate-related benchmarks and establishing the Taxonomy Regulation criteria for sustainable activities (European Union, 2020). The Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation also mandates ESG disclosure for financial market participants, introducing new frameworks for sustainability-related disclosure (European Union, 2019; Busch, 2023).

The shift towards sustainable economic and financial development has given rise to the sustainable finance market, also popularized as green finance or sustainable finance. To provide a general understanding, where traditional finance, simplified to focus solely on financial risk and return, in contrast with green finance, prioritizes financing projects with positive environmental impacts, such as reducing carbon emissions and promoting renewable energy. An evolution of green finance is sustainable finance, which integrates ESG factors into investment decisions, directing funds toward businesses committed to sustainable development, climate change mitigation, natural resource preservation, and societal well-being (La Torre and Chiappini, 2020; Thompson, 2021). Sustainable finance is not a new concept; investors have long considered factors such as assessing reputational risk and regulatory development in investment analysis. For instance, Freeman (1994) stakeholder theory supports a positive relationship between corporate social and financial performance. Many studies have shown a positive relationship between corporate social performance, stakeholder engagement, and financial performance (Deng et al., 2013; Dal Maso et al., 2017). Incorporating sustainability and ESG factors into investment analysis has enhanced long-run returns, reduced firm risk, and added value to the portfolio (Orlitzky and Benjamin, 2001; Friede et al., 2015). Additionally, stocks that undergo severe ESG controversies under-perform compared to those with high ESG ratings, and high rated ESG portfolios provide superior out-performance and diversification efficiencies (De Franco, 2020; Lee et al., 2021).

Noticeable efforts from the institution to promote sustainability using sustainable finance as a catalyst and investors inclination towards it, has made sustainable finance a cutting-edge development trend in the finance field, fuelling significant growth. This has resulted in sustainable finance, reaching a global value of \$5.8 trillion (UNCTAD, 2023). For instance, although the observations in Figure 11 comparing the returns of the S&P Europe 350 ESG Index and the traditional S&P Europe 350 shows that incorporating ESG criteria in European markets may not consistently outperform traditional benchmarks.

Figure 11: Comparison of the returns of the S&P Europe 350 ESG Index and the traditional S&P Europe 350

Nevertheless, the number of sustainable-themed funds increased by 18% in 2021, totalling 7,012 globally, with Europe accounting for 76% of the sustainable fund's universe, which amounts to 5,300 sustainable funds (UNCTAD, 2023). Morgan Stanley Institute for Sustainable Investing (2021) reports younger generations, in particular, have shown a strong inclination towards sustainable investing, further driving the momentum in this space. Overall, the substantial growth and increasing demand for sustainable investments has transformed traditional investment avenues. This transformation has extended to sectors crucial for economic growth, such as small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Being the backbone of many economies, SMEs' access to financial sources is essential for their success, survival, and growth strategies. However, just like a Green Building Neighbourhood, that in many ways share the same characteristics, they often face constraints when seeking financing opportunities (Bakhtiari et al., 2020) as indicated by the Manx Financial Group research, which revealed that two out of five SMEs pause or stop their business activities due to challenges in accessing finance (Market Screener, 2022). Despite bank lending remaining the primary external financing option for SMEs, as shown in Figure 12, the proportion allocated to new SME lending as a percentage

of total new lending remains relatively low across European nations (Yi, 2021; Degryse et al., 2017).

Figure 12: Bank lending proportion allocated to new SME lending as a percentage of total new lending across European nations

Insufficient collateral, poor creditworthiness, credit disparity, high transaction costs, and information asymmetry contribute to this challenge. Various initiatives have been proposed and implemented to enhance SMEs' access to finance and support their expansion and growth. For example, the European Commission introduced EU debt and equity financial instruments, providing guarantees for loan and equity facilities for SMEs (European Commission, 2011). The European Investment Bank also launched the SME Access to Finance Initiative, offering medium- to long-term funding and risk-sharing instruments to SMEs from EU Eastern and Southern Neighbouring Countries, supported by the European Fund for Sustainable Development (European Investment Bank, 2020). This persistent need to diversify SMEs' funding, investors, and regulatory need to prioritize ESG considerations call for innovative solutions. Thus, the study aims to propose sustainable supply chain finance (SSCF) funds. This strategic avenue addresses Green Building Neighbourhood, as equal to SMEs', financing challenges while catering to financial returns and sustainability objectives.

Supply Chain Finance (SCF): Solution to SMEs Financing

Financing is often challenging for SMEs. While large solvent corporations usually have no problem securing bank funding, SMEs often struggle to obtain the financing they need to grow and succeed (Beck and DemirgucKunt, 2006; Paulet et al., 2014). SMEs use various financing methods, including both informal and formal sources. Informal sources of financing include

personal, friends, and family financing, venture capital, private equity funds, and angel investment (Hatoum, 2019). On the other hand, formal sources include financial institutions and commercial banks (Chun and Bo, 2013). However, despite the availability of formal financing options, only a small percentage of SMEs utilize them. Most rely more on informal sources (Ayyagari et al., 2010). For instance, according to the UK Department of Business and Trade (2023), in the UK, only 9.8% of the business acquired external finance in 2020, falling to 7.5% in 2021. This lack of funding has resulted in a financing gap for SMEs. The International Finance Corporation (2022) highlighted that SMEs in developing countries face an unmet financing need of \$5.2 trillion annually, further highlighting the need for more accessible financing options for SMEs. In response to these challenges, researchers have identified SCF as a potential solution to mitigate financial constraints and improve the supply chain performance of SMEs (Moretto and Caniato, 2021; Abbasi et al., 2018). The Global SCF Forum (2016) defines SCF as "The use of financing and risk mitigation practices and techniques to optimize the management of the working capital and liquidity invested in supply chain processes and transactions." To explain, consider a scenario where a third-party logistics (3PL) company, as a supplier of logistics services, hires a transportation provider to fulfil customer orders. However, the transportation provider requires urgent cash payment within 30 days, while the 3PL has a standard payment term of 60 days with its customers. Facing a cash flow problem due to the misalignment, the 3PL company offers the transportation providers the option of supply chain financing. Through this arrangement, a financial institution immediately settles the carrier's invoice on behalf of 3PL at a lower financing cost than the traditional lending options. In return, the 3PL company commits to repaying the lender within 90 days. By opting for supply chain financing, transportation providers gain prompt access to cash, which enhances their cash flows and supports their operational needs. At the same time, the 3PL company benefits from improved working capital management by extending its payment cycle. This effectively mitigates risk and strengthens the transportation providers' and 3PL companies' financial position (Rogers et al., 2020). The introduction of SCF to alleviate the financial pressure on suppliers and enable SMEs to access credit facilities more efficiently and cost-effectively has facilitated the development of various financing agreements within the supply chain context. These include factoring, reverse factoring, forfeiting, invoice finance, early payment schemes, letters of credit, and dynamic discounting (Bicer, 2023; Klapper, 2006; Willsher, 1995). Table 1 extensively discusses the literature on the benefits of these schemes, which include reduced credit risk, improved cost efficiency, enhanced operational performance, and strengthened supplier relationships, ultimately leading to increased profitability and financial performance.

4.2.5 Driving Sustainability through SCF Mechanisms

The benefits of supply chain finance present an opportunity for the business to incentivize sustainable behaviours within global financial supply chains, thereby fostering both business growth and sustainability. For instance, according to (Zhan et al. 2018) SCF payment schemes such as Advance Payment and Reverse Factoring can promote supply chain sustainability and efficiency by reducing payment lead time. The study found that longer lead times corresponded to an increased order quantity of the retailer but lower motivation for suppliers to promote sustainability. This reduction in sustainability efforts by suppliers can ultimately lead to a decrease in the order quantity of the retailer. Additionally, the study found that a Reverse Factoring scheme with a rational payment ratio and payment term can effectively alleviate conflicts between the retailer and supplier regarding payment conditions while also promoting supplier sustainability efforts and increasing the order quantity of retailers. (Sarkar et al. 2018) proposed implementing multi-level trade credit under single setup-multiple delivery to improve the economic and environmental performance of the supply chain. Similarly, (Chen et al. 2023) findings indicate that implementing SCF can solve capital constraint issues leading to functional and structural innovations in the agricultural supply chain. This, in turn, promotes corporate social responsibility (CSR) and creates shared value. Furthermore, (Moraux et al. 2023) emphasized the benefits of collaborative financing and coordination, mainly through reverse factoring and cost-sharing contracts, in enhancing CSR efforts and profitability within supply chains. Overall, these studies highlight the immense potential of SCF and collaborative financing in driving innovation, sustainability, and CSR within supply chains, leading to the development of Sustainable Supply Chain Finance (SSCF).

SSCF refers to SCF practices and techniques that support trade transactions that minimize negative impacts and create ESG benefits for all stakeholders involved in bringing products and services to markets (Jia et al., 2020). This presents an opportunity for businesses and sustainability, as by assigning value to supply chain sustainability programs, firms can offer tangible incentives to suppliers and their buyers. Further, it has the potential to open new markets to banks and transform supply chains. Currently, many companies have embraced SSCF as a means of promoting sustainability within their financial supply chains. For instance, in partnership with IFC, BNP Paribas, HSBC, and Standard Chartered Bank, PUMA introduced a vendor financing program to incentivize suppliers with better scoring on the social and environmental compliance audits with lower interest rates. The program helped 71 vendors with a financed volume of USD 800 million until 2022 (PUMA, 2022). Similarly, to increase

sustainability in its supplier ecosystem, Henkels linked its SCF program to ESG with the help of Deutsche Bank. The sustainability-linked SCF program enables the Henkel suppliers to receive the payment immediately at a financing cost linked to their ESG rating. Thus, suppliers can lower the supply chain's financing cost by improving their ESG rating (Reuters, 2022; Deutsche Bank, 2022).

4.2.6 Rationale for the SSCF Fund

The shift from SCF to SSCF is a significant strategic change that entails considering factors when making financial decisions. The potential and demand of the SSCF market are demonstrated by the (Astute Analytica 2023) report, which states that the SSCF market was valued at US\$ 1,200.1 million in 2022 and is expected to surpass US\$ 4,856.6 million by 2031, reflecting a remarkable CAGR of 17.47%. On the contrary, in 2022, the global sustainable finance market size was US\$ 4,562.85 billion and is expected to reach US\$ 29,111.04 billion by 2032 at a CAGR of 20.36% (Precedence Research, 2023). The projected growth rates of SSCF compared to global sustainable finance markets show that it has substantial potential for expansion and becoming a significant component of the broader sustainable finance market. As the demand for sustainable finance solutions grows, so does the potential of SSCF markets to attract investors seeking ESG-aligned opportunities and borrowers looking for financing solutions that support their sustainability initiatives. Further, the difference between the market size of SSCF and global sustainable finance markets represents untapped opportunities within SCF, which lenders and borrowers can capitalize on by developing innovative financial products or solutions tailored to SSCF. In this context, the study proposes a dedicated fund based on SSCF.

4.2.7 Green washing and Enhancing Transparency

To achieve sustainable goals, several new methods of financing green projects have been introduced in the financial markets, such as green banks, green bonds, green funds, etc. Over the past five years, the issuance of green bonds has as shown in Figure 13 surged by 288%, reaching a total of 540.92 billion US Dollars in 2022.

Figure 13: Development of issuance of green bonds from 2010 to 2022

However, these methods have faced significant criticism for their lack of standardization, and high issuance costs (Sangiorgi and Schopohl, 2023; Bansal et al., 2023), hindering the progress of the green bond market. Additionally, environmental regulations intended to promote green finance are weakened by greenwashing practices. For instance, (Xu et al. 2022) found that greenwashing practices among non-manufacturing enterprises weaken environmental regulations intended to promote green finance. (Hu et al. 2023) supported their findings by discovering that environmental tax reforms led to increased green-washing among high polluting companies, notably smaller non-state-owned enterprises with lower financial constraints. Further, even though Romanian banks have started adopting green, social, and sustainability-labelled financial products, Nica (2023) identified that these stocks are below potential. (Jia and Li 2023) emphasized that green innovation positively influences financing, while greenwashing poses challenges in securing loans. Furthermore, (Liu et al. 2023) conducted an overview of greenwashing and identified the external governance factors, market pressures, and internal governance mechanisms that influence green-washing behaviours. This phenomenon undermines the credibility of green finance initiatives and threatens global sustainability agendas. To combat green-washing and enhance transparency, there is a pressing need for a dedicated financial vehicle to provide clear, standardized information about investment projects' environmental and social impacts.

4.2.8 Gap in SSCF development

While there is a growing body of research on SSCF, there remains a gap in dedicated investment explicitly tailored to support SSCF. The available research explored the diverse aspects of SSCF.

Several studies have contributed to the conceptual understanding and development of SSCF. For instance, Jia et al. (2020) delves into the concept of SSCF, identifying its drivers, outcomes, and potential of using SCF as an enhancer of sustainability. Similarly, (Tseng et al. 2018) explores the critical attributes of SSCF. They emphasize that economic and social aspects are two primary attributes, with the economic aspect exerting a more significant influence on SSCF. Another study by (Tseng et al. 2019) delves into SSCF, explicitly focusing on benefit and cost analysis. They provide a comprehensive criteria system for evaluating SSCF aspects, including financial decision synchronization, pricing data, product/service quality, dependence dispersion, and interdepartmental interactions. (Negash et al. 2024) emphasize the driving roles of collaboration value innovation, financial stability, and operational capacity in enabling SSCF. (Abdel-Basset et al. 2020) highlight an increased focus on financial practices and product/service aspects in achieving SSCF. Moreover, some studies focused on the role of technology in enhancing SSCF. (Reza-Gharehbagh et al. 2023) explored the role of digital platforms in facilitating green entrepreneurship through SSCF. Their study addressed challenges faced by SMEs seeking financial backing. It advocated for government intervention to foster sustainable SSCF through regulatory measures and digital platform financing. (Olan et al. 2024) highlight the need for technological advancements like Artificial Intelligence (AI) to enhance SCF processes. By adopting a fuzzy set theoretical approach, the study unpacks the relationship validity for sustainable SCF frameworks, emphasizing AI's significant economic opportunities for optimizing supply networks. (Soni et al. 2022) underscores SMEs' need to adopt Industry 4.0 technologies to bolster SSCF. It introduces a decision-making model to aid in technology selection, emphasizing the importance of this process for SMEs' growth and sustainability.

Furthermore, some studies addressed risk assessment and management within SSCF. (Wang et al. 2022) proposed an integrated BWM-CRITIC approach based on set theory. They develop a comprehensive framework for evaluating SSCF risks by identifying and analysing various risk factors. The model emphasizes the importance of understanding collateral and accounts receivable stability, cooperation, internal environment, information sharing, risks, and control measures within the SCF domain. (Yang et al. 2021) highlight the importance of effectively managing credit risk to achieve SSCF goals and emphasize the role of SSCF in this process. Using the lasso-logistic model, they identify key factors influencing SMEs' credit risk, including order data matching, contract enforcement ratio, contract defaults, business concentration degree, and administrative penalties. Similarly, (Xia et al. 2022) constructed a credit risk assessment indicator system for SSCF for green agriculture. They emphasized the significance of the credit rating of core companies as the most critical indicator in assessing SSCF. This indicator holds

substantial weight in determining risk levels and financial decisions. Lastly, the role of government intervention and policy frameworks in promoting sustainable SSCF has been another area of focus. (Qin and Hong 2023) highlighted the positive influence of government participation in promoting sustainable development, with penalties and subsidies serving as effective incentives for financial institutions and core enterprises to ensure sustainable practices and address environmental pollution. Rebelo (2020) analyses how legal mechanisms in SCF agreements can implement and enforce green policy frameworks to provide for the effective environmental governance of transboundary trade practices. (Medina et al. 2023) also supported involving new actors to positively influence the development of SSCF (SSCF) solutions. Third-party information providers, NGOs, and certification bodies can assume different brokerage roles to promote sustainable practices and ensure environmental governance.

This highlights a significant gap in the research, as while the studies mentioned above clearly recognize the importance of SSCF, there is a lack of financial tools specifically designed to support sustainable supply chains, such as an SCF fund. Addressing this gap could enable stakeholders to implement sustainable practices across supply chains, promoting positive environmental and social impacts while enhancing financial performance.

4.2.9 SSCF Fund using Block Chain Technology

Considering these, the promising solution to overcome the SME's financing risks while mitigating green-washing, enhancing transparency in financing green initiatives, and bridging the gap in sustainable supply chain finance development is the establishment of an SSCF Fund leveraging blockchain technology (Martino, 2021). Blockchain technology has become increasingly popular in recent years for supply chain finance (SCF), as multiple studies have indicated its potential to improve efficiency and address various challenges. For example, (Rijanto 2021) suggests that blockchain technology can aid in addressing automation problems such as Know Your Customer (KYC) procedures, accounting, and transaction settlement, while (Bhatia et al. 2024) highlights its role in reducing transaction costs associated with finance assessment, information search, negotiation, and contracting. Additionally, according to (Lahkani et al. 2020), blockchain enhances logistics efficiency and digital documentation, accelerates payment processes, and ensures reliability and transparency in data transfer. Moreover, (Trautmann and Lasch 2021) emphasizes that blockchain enabled SCF models mitigate cyber-security risks, increase transparency and trust, and reduce the potential for transaction manipulation among participants. These findings indicate that blockchain technology has the potential to

revolutionize SCF practices and improve financial conditions for stakeholders by enhancing transparency and security.

Researchers have proposed various SSCF models based on the advantages of blockchain. For instance, Fu et al. (2022) proposed a blockchain-based financing scheme designed specifically for logistics companies, which simplifies financing processes while protecting data privacy. (Guo et al. 2022) introduced a blockchain and Internet of Things (IoT)-based information management framework (BC4Regu) that integrates capital, information, logistics, and trade flow within the supply chain, reducing operation costs and addressing information asymmetry issues. Lastly, (Zheng et al. 2022) proposed a model that focuses on improving the credit-reporting ability of the supply chain financial credit system using blockchain technology. Thus, enhances data integrity, decentralization, transparency, and security.

Moreover, leading blockchain-based SCF projects like Komgo and Skuchain exemplify the industry's recognition of blockchain's transformative potential. These initiatives streamline trade finance processes, offer digital SCF solutions, and increase transparency and efficiency within supply chains (Wass, 2019; Bermingham, 2018; Business Insider, 2017). Walmart's SSCF program with initiatives such as the Walmart Sustainability Index Program (WSIP), Project Gigaton, and Walmart Canada's partnership with DLT Labs also serves as a successful example of the integration of SSCF with Blockchain. The WSIP program promotes sustainability by offering preferential funding rates to suppliers undertaking sustainability initiatives and demonstrating progress toward their targets. It also provides financial support through standard green loans to fund innovative projects to reduce environmental impact. The second initiative, Project Gigaton, launched in 2017, aims to reduce one billion tons of greenhouse gases by 2030. It requires collaboration with suppliers to analyse the environmental impact of products throughout their life cycle. Additionally, Walmart Canada's partnership with DLT Labs created complete transparency between the company and its partners, resulting in expedited payments, extensive cost savings, and other benefits within the supply chain. Financial analysis from 2016 to 2020 showed improved profitability and liquidity attributed to blockchain implementation. Overall, this case study highlights the transformative impact of blockchain technology on supply chains (Bal and Pawlicka, 2021). Hence, both the academic and industry recognition of blockchain-enabled SCF supports the rationale for establishing a SSCF Fund.

In Conclusion

Climate change, often referred to as a "Threat Multiplier," is the most pressing issue facing humanity today, and immediate action is needed to combat its impact (Goodman and Baudu,

2023). In 2015, world leaders who participated in the Paris Agreement recognized the financial potential to mitigate climate change and promote sustainable development (van Calster and Reins 2021). In response to the agreement, international institutions such as the European Union have taken measures to encourage companies to integrate ESG factors into their operations, such as climate-related benchmarks, Taxonomy Regulation criteria for sustainable activities (European Union 2020) and the Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (European Union 2019; Busch 2023).

Amidst these efforts, the role of SMEs in the transition towards sustainability cannot be overstated. Given their contribution to global economic activity, social well-being, and environmental footprint, they have tremendous potential as drivers of green and inclusive growth (Koirala 2019). However, SMEs often face challenges in accessing finance, hindering their ability to adopt sustainable practices (Bakhtiari et al. 2020). Supply chain finance (SCF) has emerged as a promising solution to address this gap, offering SMEs access to financing while incentivizing sustainability within global supply chains (Zhan et al. 2018; Sarkar et al. 2018; Chen et al. 2023; Moraux et al. 2023).

Considering these developments, the concept of sustainable supply chain finance (SSCF) has gained traction in recent years. SSCF offers a compelling opportunity to align financial incentives with sustainability goals, enabling SMEs to integrate environmentally and socially responsible practices into their operations. However, despite the growing interest in SSCF, the literature highlights a gap in dedicated investment vehicles tailored to support sustainable supply chains. Additionally, there is a pressing need for a dedicated green financial vehicle that can address the issues of greenwashing and enhance transparency. To address these gaps, we propose the establishment of SSCF funds as an innovative solution. Leveraging blockchain technology, SSCF funds offer transparency, security, and efficiency in financing green initiatives (Martino 2021). Blockchain-enabled SCF models have demonstrated significant potential in streamlining processes, reducing costs, and enhancing transparency within supply chains (Rijanto 2021; Bhatia et al. 2024; Lahkani et al. 2020). Furthermore, initiatives such as Walmart's SSCF program showcase the transformative impact of blockchain technology in promoting sustainability across supply chains (Pawlicka and Bal 2021).

In conclusion, the establishment of SSCF funds represents a critical step towards aligning financial practices with sustainability objectives. By leveraging blockchain technology and integrating ESG considerations into financial decision-making, SSCF funds have the potential to drive positive change, foster transparency, and facilitate investments in truly sustainable

initiatives. As we strive to achieve the objectives outlined in the Paris Agreement and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, SSCF funds offer a pathway towards a more resilient and equitable future for all stakeholders.

4.3 Changes in the Strategic Vision and KPIs of the LLs

In this subsection we review the six PROBONO living labs. We present the original ambitions, intended technologies to be applied and the corresponding KPIs, and report on changes to the technologies and KPIs that have occurred during the project so far. This is intended to show, by way of example, the extent to which individual KPIs can change due to changing conditions in the specific development of GBNs. Care must be taken to ensure that the overarching goal of achieving GBNs is maintained. The monitoring concept and the associated KPIs are described in detail in Deliverable D6.3 (Antolin and et al. 2024).

While various challenges due to delays and funding issues have arisen, overall, there are no *major* changes from the original plan in terms of the technologies being applied and their assigned KPIs.

In summary; (a) Aarhus introduced social KPIs to better capture the aimed impact of various socially-oriented technologies (health, well-being, Indoor Environment Quality indicators, etc.) and this also was deemed to align well with the AU human-centred tools being developed; and (b) Prague LL through internal discussions between partners within PROBONO the valuable opportunity of applying the Ventilation Assessment Tool was discovered and a strategic plan was made between CTU and ITA. This also enabled two new social KPIs to be included in the Prague LL which was determined to be a valuable extension of impacts being monitored by the LL and other PROBONO partners.

The review of the initial KPIs per LL revealed the following.

- a. The Dublin LL is focussing on determining how carefully selected interventions can be widely adopted locally to move towards creating a Decarbonizing Zone which will be integral to the creation of a GBN in Dún Laoghaire. Social innovations such as a Post Occupancy Evaluation in retrofitted social housing will also act as a proof of concept for wider adoption in the creation of a GBN. There are no major deviations from the original plan, rather there has been significant refinement on the application of the selected technologies and the alignment of KPIs.

- b. Madrid LL was originally focused on the Development of Las Tablas Oeste and the establishment of common integrated energy infrastructures to fully cover the district's thermal demand through geothermic energy and the electricity demand through solar energy via photovoltaics on buildings and the urban space. The urbanization project is significantly behind schedule and cannot be completed on time as stated in the Grant Agreement (GA). Several alternatives to reduce the impact of delays are being explored, and fortunately, most selected innovations can be tested during the urbanization phase.
- c. Porto LL originally intended to be an open innovation space, where stakeholders develop and test new solutions to address key challenges, such as sustainability, energy resilience, and climate change. LL activities also intended to promote and foster social inclusiveness by empowering citizens to use different products and/or services and integrate them into the process (e.g., develop infrastructure and adequate services necessary to help citizens in the city). It envisioned to develop the conditions for a more energy efficient corporate campus, including Renewable Energy Community (REC); Energy Tech Hub; Monitoring, controlling, AI/forecasting tools development, and study of consumer behaviour; Decentralized energy community; Support of biodiversity. Impact 4 (high energy performance) was added, to be achieved by adding renewable energy sources and applying energy efficiency measures; Also, PCM technologies aligned with Expected Impact 6 (Reduction of the embodied energy in buildings) were reassigned to Expected Impact 1 (Primary energy savings), owing to PCM outcome of saving energy.
- d. The original concept for the Aarhus LL consisted of (a) VisBlue flow batteries - advanced sustainable energy storage devices that address life cycle environment (LCA) and life cycle cost (LCC) for the entire site (i.e. across all buildings that form the neighbourhood of Campus Viborg) (b) upcycling design strategies that repurpose existing structures for new housing that address life cycle environmental (LCA) and social qualities (SLCA), (c) human-centred analysis tools that make as-designed social values explicit and visible to a wide range of stakeholders, and therefore also ensuring that social values are present and traceable throughout the design phase and operational phase (SLCA). Initially, Aarhus LL did not include social KPIs, however, this was changed to capture performance indicators of the human-centred analysis tools that are being developed and piloted in Aarhus LL.

- e. The Brussels LL originally focused on neighbourhood engagement activities within the Commune of Auderghem, and specifically the roof of the De l'Autre Côté de l'École (ACE), which is still the original roof when the building was constructed in 1998 and is deteriorating, leaky and due for renovation. The renovation aimed to make the area useful for the school's educational needs while also being in line with the environmental and regulative requirements of the European Green Deal. They worked with the VIAS Institute on mobility as a means for collaborative engagement and discussion. The intended technologies to be applied involve: (a) the Highly Evaporative Green Roof, (b) Energy Performance and Monitoring, (c) the Energy Demand Response Platform applied to relevant doors and windows on all floors, and relevant main utility inflows for electrical power and gas, and (d) the Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) monitoring and behaviours study. There are no other reported changes to the applied technologies or KPIs.
- f. The Prague LL is a collaboration between Czech Technical University (CTU) and Prague District 6. The focus is deep renovation of "Building B" within the Faculty of Civil Engineering at CTU. The originally planned technologies are included: (a) building integrated photovoltaic façade, (b) Insulation and green and cool roof-centric innovations, (c) bio-solar roof combining green and photovoltaic elements, (d) energy planning for the green building neighbourhoods, (e) Digital Twins for Energy management, (f) Augmented reality for facility management. During the project a new technology was included with two social KPIs. No other changes to the technologies and KPIs have been made. There are significant funding challenges, and a rejection of some initial design plans by the "client" stakeholders in Civil Engineering at CTU, although so far this has not been reported as resulting in a change of applied technologies or KPIs.

5 Conclusions

GBN is a comprehensive concept for sustainable neighbourhoods. The goal is to design new neighbourhoods and redevelop existing ones in such a way that a climate-neutral energy supply is achieved and the neighbourhood makes a positive energy contribution to the surrounding energy system. However, to achieve a GBN, many other aspects must also be considered and criteria met. For example, a high level of comfort must be guaranteed in the buildings, for example with regard to air conditioning and other aspects influencing the stay of users, which is

why the simulation and optimization of the technical systems should be human-centered. In chapter 3.1, 23 aspects of social sustainability, among others, were identified that can be taken into account. These are to be differentiated according to three levels of social values: human centered, city and neighbourhood centered, and global and governmental centered.

The maturity of the GBN should be measurable based on international standards. Therefore, the ISO 37100 series standard is used in PROBONO as a basis for describing and quantifying criteria (see chapter 3.2). The ISO 37107 Maturity Model for Smart Sustainable Communities (MMSSC – see Figure 5) provides a top-level maturity model for smart sustainable communities (ISO 2019). It can be used for self-assessment by communities to evaluate how mature they are in adopting good practices for sustainable and smart-enabled development. The ISO 37100 series, more specifically the ISO 37101 standard enable a cross-analysis of GBN strategies, programmes, projects, plans, and services against the six sustainability / ESG purposes and twelve areas of actions (ISO 2016). The mapping of PROBONO KPIs and ISO 37101 sustainability principles is shown in Table 3 in chapter 3.2.2, which proves that the metrics of ISO 37101 and 37107 are very helpful for evaluating GBNs.

In the face of rapidly worsening climate change, it is imperative that buildings, neighbourhoods and cities adapt to the changing climate. Depending on local conditions, heavy rainfall events and flooding and/or periods of drought are increasingly to be expected. Depending on the climate zone, the microclimate, with an increasing number of hot days and an increasing need for cooling, also plays an growing burden that not only affects the quality of life but can also pose a life-threatening burden for weakened, sick and elderly people. Therefore, measures to adapt to climate change and to increase resilience as described in Chapter 0 are of great importance. These include, among other things, structural measures such as robust building design, structural reinforcement, green infrastructure, water management, energy efficiency and renewable energy, and regular maintenance practices. Furthermore, practice-based measures are also described, such as disaster preparedness and redundancy preparedness.

Any construction project consumes resources and impacts existing ecosystems. It is therefore important that synergies are exploited and that the fruitful coexistence of technical and ecological systems is facilitated and promoted. In GBNs, this is possible through the implementation of green roofs and green facades, if these are designed in such a way that they contribute to maintaining and increasing biodiversity. The importance of biodiversity and the possibilities for its promotion in GBNs is therefore discussed in chapter 3.4. Evidence demonstrates that a wide variety of insects including uncommon species find favourable

conditions in green roofs therefore supporting the idea that green roofs can support biodiversity in the urban space as shown in chapter 3.4.1. Chapter 3.4.2 describes biodiversity in the different stages of project development and makes clear what needs to be considered in order to actually achieve success in GBNs in terms of biodiversity. For example, it is necessary to understand the GBN's ecosystem and its surroundings, to know the local geography and to inform project stakeholders and future users about the site's initial richness and associated challenges to explain design choices.

Other technical aspects such as the use of renewable energies and the increase of energy efficiency, resource-efficient construction methods and intelligent planning and operation using digital twins are not specifically addressed in this document, but are being addressed in other PROBONO work packages and are equally imperative to achieving the GBN objectives.

An important aspect for the successful practical implementation of GBNs is the availability of suitable financing instruments that adequately take into account the advantages of GBNs. Initial investments in efficiency and sustainability technologies are often higher, which is why investment decisions by price-sensitive actors or the public sector are often not possible without further developed financing mechanisms. Therefore, the consideration of additional criteria that take into account the sustainability of solutions is crucial when evaluating investments.

ESG reporting is an important tool in this regard. It is no longer a nice-to-have, it is a must-have. As of 2023, 96% of S&P 500 companies are engaged in voluntary ESG reporting, and with this rise in popularity comes new ambitions and pressures (Waelbroeck 2023). Chapter 4.1 describes how the ESG perspective can be used to develop GBNs and improve financing conditions. It is pointed out that the ESG perspective ensures that GBNs are designed and operated in a way that minimizes their ecological footprint and contributes positively to climate change mitigation efforts.

In addition to the economic assessment instruments for investments in buildings and districts, the availability of financing instruments is also crucial for successful implementation. For this reason, the investment conditions in GBN development were examined and presented in great detail in chapter 4.2. In doing so, a usual financing of Green Buildings was compared with green finance instruments. These are, for example, sustainable property funds, green bonds/loans, green mortgages, public-private partnerships or bioclimatic (green) building funds (GBFs) (see chapter 4.2.1).

Green financial instruments for green building projects are also offered at the European level (see chapter 4.2.2). For example, the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) 2021-2027 and

NextGenerationEU (NGEU), Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) and Green Bonds, European Energy Efficiency Fund (EEEF), European Investment Bank (EIB) Green Investments and European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) Green Economy Transition (GET) Plan are available as financing instruments.

Furthermore, chapter 4.2.3 explains challenges and solutions in financing green buildings and chapters 4.2.4 to 4.2.9 provide an overview of sustainable supply chain finance (SSCF). In summary, it is stated that the establishment of SSCF funds represents a critical step towards aligning financial practices with sustainability objectives. By leveraging blockchain technology and integrating ESG considerations into financial decision-making, SSCF funds have the potential to drive positive change, foster transparency, and facilitate investments in truly sustainable initiatives. As we strive to achieve the objectives outlined in the Paris Agreement and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, SSCF funds offer a pathway towards a more resilient and equitable future for all stakeholders (chapter 4.2.9).

When developing GBNs, it is also important to consider that the strategy and the set KPIs may change during project development and that adjustments may be necessary. The practical experience gained from the PROBONO Living Labs is very valuable in understanding the nature and extent to which framework conditions may change. Therefore, chapter 4.3 describes the changes to the GBN planning and implementation after 36 months of the project in relation to the vision and the associated KPIs set at the beginning of the project. This is a plea for constantly adapting the implementation strategy and the KPIs to the real conditions, along with the planning. However, it is important to maintain the overarching goals, such as climate neutrality or a high quality of stay for users, and not to question them.

All the aspects mentioned, as well as many other experiences from the PROBONO project in other WPs, were taken into account in the development of the GBN Target Model. Chapter 2 provides an overview of the GBN Target Model concept, while chapter 2.3 describes how the GBN Target Model is developed. Based on an assessment of the neighbourhood, which should be done using the ISO 37101 metric, and a comparative analysis of alternative solutions and consideration of framework conditions at the local (City Vision & Plan), national and also European (Green Deal) level, an optimized GBN concept is to be developed as a target model for the specific neighbourhood. Once this has been created for the individual buildings and/or the community of several buildings, an implementation strategy can be developed.

In summary, it can be said that neighbourhood development is generally a complex task. This is further complicated by the objective of the GBNs, since, in addition to developing solutions for

the technical systems (construction of the buildings, infrastructure for the supply of energy, water, data, etc., mobility issues, etc.), sustainability aspects (climate neutrality, climate adaptation, microclimate, biodiversity, etc.) and, in particular, social aspects (affordability of housing and utilities, quality of living, participation, social mix, education, healthy living environment, etc.) must be taken into account in the conception and design of the buildings and open spaces. In addition, intelligent and future-oriented planning and operating structures also play a major role in the development of GBNs, in particular the development and implementation of digital twins. In order for project developers to adopt GBNs as an objective for their neighbourhood developments, financing mechanisms are needed that overcompensate for possible initial additional costs, for example, due to a better ESG rating based on image or improved funding conditions.

By nature, an evaluation methodology and metrics are needed to develop an optimized and, in the case of existing conflicting goals, a well-balanced design for a specific neighbourhood, taking into account all relevant dimensions that make up a GBN. This document explains some relevant aspects and associated evaluation criteria and presents a GBN target model that was developed in PROBONO.

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